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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
CA	Consortium Agreement
CHIL	Control Hardware-in-the-Loop
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DG	Distributed Generation
DoA	Description of Action
DRTS	Digital Real Time Simulator
DSO	Distribution System Operator
DUT	Device Under Test
EC	European Commission
ERN	European Researcher's Night
ESS	Energy Storage System
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
FS	Functional Scenario
GA	Grant Agreement
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real Time Simulation
GDHIL	Geographically Distributed Hardware-in-the-Loop
GP	General Public
H2020	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HVDC	High Voltage Direct Current
HW	Hardware
HSS	High School Student
HUT	Hardware under Test
IA	Interface Algorithm
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ILO	Intended Learning Outcome
JRA	Joint Research Activity
NA	Networking Activity
P	Professionals
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PhD	Doctor of Philosophy
PSI	Physical Shifting Impedance
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy System
RTS	Real-time Simulation
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
UN	United Nations
VSI	Virtual Shifting Impedance
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

ERIGrid 2.0 training and educational activities aim to inform a broad audience about best practices and latest advancement in methods, approaches and tools for the development, validation and roll-out of smart energy systems solutions.

An *educational strategy* is presented, offering a tool for coordination and alignment of the training activities. The proposed and applied method combines qualitative organisation of topics, target audiences and educational scope, with a quantitative reflection on the areas of training developed in the project. By means of surveys and systematic analysis of reported training activity plans, an overview of the topical areas developed in the project is documented, and contrasted with the intended developments. The summary provides an intermediary status view of the planned and executed training activities. In short, all intended target groups have been addressed, and most types of intended training activity types have been developed. Gaps appear to remain between the intended and the achieved coverage of research areas by the planned training activities. To highlight a few, topics of 'demand response', and 'flexibility management', as well as 'inverter dominated systems' have not yet been addressed. An analysis of intended cognitive level of competence (using Bloom's taxonomy) reveals that the training activities are mostly aimed at comprehension and application experiences, with a few exceptions also considering analysis and synthesis skills. Given the scope and available time for most training activities, this level is as expected.

The *on-site training activities* reported in this document span a wide range of training events, including training for high-school students, the general public as well as industry professionals and researcher. The training activities span a good range and number: One training school for PhD students and researchers was hosted, and three further are planned. Two events each were hosted for high-school students and the general public, respectively. Three independent workshops were hosted. At international conferences, three panel sessions were organised and one tutorial given. The so far presented and planned training activities are already close to fulfilling the intended project objectives.

The *staff exchange* reports on an internal programme for training and collaboration across partners, where the exchange of experiences and expertise is in focus. A number of staff exchanges has been carried out – here the main strategy has been the organisation of group staff exchanges for specific project-wide initiatives. Overall, twelve staff exchanges were applied for and granted – all as part of a single group staff exchange.

Overall, the reported and planned training activities represent only a fraction of the available material. This report will be followed up by a similar type report, towards the end the project period.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

ERIGrid 2.0 training and educational activities aim to inform a broad audience about best practices and latest advancement in methods, approaches and tools for the development, validation and roll-out of smart energy system solutions. The project ambition is to apply state of the art teaching approaches and techniques, such as active and student-driven learning, self-study, and digital learning platforms. The training content can be adapted to various audiences.

This document reports on three areas of training related activities: the educational strategy, all on-site training activities carried out, and the ERIGrid 2.0 internal staff exchange.

The *educational strategy* aims to provide a qualitative and quantitative reflection on the areas of training developed in the project. By means of surveys and systematic reporting, an overview of the topical areas developed in the project is documented. The templates and forms developed in the educational strategy offer a common structure for feedback and the future improvement of training.

The *on-site training activities* reported in this document span a wide range of training events, including training for high-school students, the general public as well as industry professionals and researchers.

The *staff exchange* reports on an internal programme for training and collaboration across partners, where the exchange of experience and expertise is in focus.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the educational strategy and the present state of the focus areas, Section 3 describes the planned and executed training activities, and Section 4 describes the structure and current results of the staff exchange programme. The deliverable is concluded in Section 5. Finally, additional content is provided in the Appendix A and Appendix B, where original templates, activity plans, activity reports, and staff exchange reports are included.

2 Educational Strategy

The educational strategy aims to provide orientation and coordination of the ERIGrid 2.0 educational activities. The concept behind this approach is to assemble bottom-up developed educational elements such as surveys, training objectives and learning modules, and to develop a coherent picture of these inputs. The educational strategy is based on an analysis of training content in form of stated training objectives and intended learning outcomes, and aims to contrast content of already the delivered training activities with the planned and intended training activities. The result informs a gap analysis, recognising the areas where the project can focus additional efforts to realise the intended training outcomes.

The rationale of this approach is based on the following observation: training activities and modules are more effectively developed in small independent teams, however, there is a chance for an improved quality by delivering alignment of training objectives (direction) as well as feedback collections and assessment can be across training activities.

Figure 1 illustrates the process behind this management approach. The approach rests on three pillars:

- An initial questionnaire, setting the partners' ambition,
- The activity plan (training activity form), reporting *training objectives*, and *Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)* for each activity, and
- The educational strategy.

The figure also illustrates the material and activity development in two rounds, where the first round includes educational materials and training events reported until this point. Here the definition of relevant topic areas and validation methods was set in the initial questionnaire, and which was then applied for the analysis of the activity plans. The activity plans for on-site training activities are included here, in Appendix A.2, the activity plans for other materials (e.g., webinars and online tools), are appended to the companion deliverable (*D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education, 2023*).

Figure 1: Overview of the educational strategy approach.

An essential tool in the analysis of ILOs is seen in Bloom's taxonomy ("Bloom's taxonomy: Original and revised", 2005), which enables the structured analysis of statements about ILOs. The taxonomy has been used in various context in education, and exists in at least two versions ("original" and "revise"). In this work, a "wheel" representation of Bloom's original taxonomy (cf. Figure 1; the graphical representation of Bloom's taxonomy wheel was adopted from a web source¹) was appended to the training activity plan template (cf. Appendix A.1.1), to support those who devised training activities in describing the ILOs of their training activity.

In this section, the results from questionnaire, and the first round of activity plans will be introduced in a comparative quantitative summary. The resulting gap between intended and already planned and executed activities is reported. Each section introduces the relevant concepts for which the gap analysis is performed. In Section 2.1, training activity types and mode, as well as target groups are introduced. Section 2.2 presents the analysis technical area of in terms of training activity scope and objectives, and Section 2.3 reflects on the ILOs planned for all training activities.

2.1 Types of Training Activities and Intended Target Groups

This section introduces all the types of training activities considered in ERIGrid 2.0, and compares the planned and reported number of activities in each category.

2.1.1 Training Activity Types

The training activities revisited in this report consider both the physical on-site training session and online training offers. Types of educational activities associated with a physical location are further reported on the following sections. The activities can be defined as:

1. *Training Schools*: Summer or winter schools attended by researchers, mainly Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) students,
2. *Training of High School Students*: Training activities specific oriented to high school students and the general public,
3. *Training of Professionals*: Training activities for professionals (e.g., Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) or power systems professionals),
4. *Workshops and Seminars*: A separate event with invited speakers, open to the public; attended by researchers or industry,
5. *Special and Panel Sessions*: Session organised as part of a (scientific) conference, and
6. *Tutorials*: Training event organised as part of a (scientific) conference, typically placed before the start of the conference.

Purely digital training resources and activities are reported in (*D-NA3.2 Education and Training Material for E-learning and Laboratory Education*, 2023), however, they are reflected in the educational strategy as well like:

1. *Webinars*: Engaging online events in which a speaker or a group of speakers deliver presentations to an audience, which interact with them through questions, polls or any other interactive means,

¹<https://www.wbtsystems.com/learning-hub/blogs/blooms-taxonomy>

2. *Education Tools*: Software programs that are used by educators and students to facilitate the educational process; usually, they are designed for carrying out various types of analyses (steady-state, dynamic, etc.),
3. *Interactive Notebooks*: Human-readable documents that contain code based parts (Python, MATLAB, etc.) enriched with text elements (paragraph, equations, figures, links, etc.),
4. *Virtual Laboratories*: Interactive, digitally simulated activities similar to the ones that take place in actual physical laboratories,
5. *Remote Laboratories*: Online access to the physical infrastructure of a remote laboratory,
6. *Videos*: Videos or recordings of technical topics or developments for educational purposes,
7. *Co-simulation Education*: Refers to the use of co-simulation tools for hands-on laboratory educational purposes,
8. *Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) Education*: Refers to the use of HIL setups (Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL), Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL)) for hands-on laboratory educational purposes, and
9. *Hardware (HW) Setups Education*: Refers to the use of pure hardware setups for the hands-on laboratory education.

Mode of Training Activity Execution

An additional classifier field quantifies how the activity is held, i.e., whether the activity was virtual, face-to-face or material disseminated as open access to the public.

Analysis of Activity Plans

Once the obtained were results, it was concluded that the balance between the number of activities held virtually and face-to-face is still tilted toward virtual training activities, still as aftermath of the lockdown conditions during the first project years. Internal discussion revealed that further (not yet planned) face-to-face events are intended, though not yet planned, and therefore not in the data. The summary of the analysis is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Analysis of other classifiers covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning up till December 2022.

The training activities considered in the educational strategy analysis in Section 2 encompass all of the listed training activities. However, the activities reported in Section 3 and Section 4 only cover Face-to-Face activities. The results indicate that ERIGrid 2.0 training activities cover all three aforementioned formats where it predominates the online with 16 delivered and in planning activities. Subsequently it follows the face-to-face format accounting for 9 activities and it closes the open access material with 7 activities.

2.1.2 Target Groups

ERIGrid 2.0 aims to reach a broad audience, so then it involves several target groups in the training activities that are carried out. Main target groups are listed below:

1. *Young Researchers – PhD Students*: This group covers not only PhD students but also young professionals dedicated to the research sector,
2. *Undergraduate Students*: Includes students that are pursuing a bachelor degree,
3. *Power System Professionals*: As some of the training activity topics are oriented to Power systems and smart grids areas, the professionals in these fields are considered a specific target group,
4. *ICT Professionals*: Similar to power system professionals, ICT professionals becomes a target group of interest, and
5. *High School Students*: Some of the training activities organised under ERIGrid 2.0 projects aim to raise the awareness of the importance of renewable energies as well as attract youth to these research areas. For this reason, another target group includes high school students.

Initial Plan (First Round Questionnaire)

“Young researchers — PhD Students” was selected by 10 partners. Undergraduate students was selected by 7 partners. “Power System Professionals” was selected by 9 partners and “ICT professionals” was selected by 2 partners. Finally, “High School Students” was selected by 3 partners. Figure 3 provides an overview of the first round questionnaire results.

Figure 3: Results of questionnaire about target groups addressed in the ERIGrid 2.0 training activities according to the consortium partners.

Analysis of Activity Plans

Figure 4 shows the distribution of the activities according to the target groups established at the beginning of the project, taking into consideration that a single activity may cover multiple groups depending on its scope.

Figure 4: Analysis of target groups covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning (Status: Feb. 2023).

Overall, the results show that both young researchers and professionals stands for the main target groups in the training activities. From the training activities already delivered and in planing status 21 involve power system professionals, 17 target young research, 13 are oriented to undergraduate students, 7 implicate ICT professionals, and 3 involve high school students.

Comparing the statistics of the target groups addressed in planned activities, Figure 4, with the initially intended target groups, Figure 3, only minor differences are observed, and all intended target groups have benefited from training activities by ERIGrid 2.0.

2.2 Analysis of Training Activity Scope and Objectives

To set the ambition and to enable a quantitative analysis of the training activity scope, the project defined a number of classifiers for training activity topics. Considering the scope of ERIGrid 2.0, technical topics are viewed from both a technology application point of view and from the perspective of testing and validation methods. Also the project defined a set of six “Functional Scenarios (FSs)” at the outset (*D-NA4.1 Functional Scenarios, 2020*). This section reports the quantitative analysis and comparison of initial survey and reported activity plans.

The initial survey questionnaires were answered individually by each partner, who are also responsible for implementing the respective activities.

2.2.1 Functional Scenarios

To specify the project ambition, at the outset of the project, the partners formulated several FS, each of which combine under a coherent theme stakeholders, technical and business areas with related use case and test cases (*D-NA4.1 Functional Scenarios, 2020*):

1. *FS1 - Ancillary Services Provided by Distributed Energy Resource (DER)s and Active Grid Assets*: Electric Vehicle (EV) integration, Renewable Energy System (RES) integration, inverter functionalities to provide system support; DER flexibility and controllability.
2. *FS2 - Microgrids and Energy Community*: local and peer-to-peer setting; fostering self-consumption, offering flexibility services; coordinated services: self-balancing, frequency restoration and support, congestion management, black start support, multi-energy resource optimisation, and power quality support.
3. *FS3 - Sector Coupling*: Flexibility across energy systems (e.g., district heating vs. electric distribution network), multi-energy systems; industrial flexibility (thermal and process flexibility).
4. *FS4 - Frequency and Voltage Stability in Inverter Dominated Power Systems*: Provision of ancillary services by DER for frequency and voltage support in low inertia systems.
5. *FS5 - Aggregation and Flexibility Management*: Aggregator business, validation, trading and optimisation, grid support functions, geographically distributed testing etc.; dispatch functionality; DER with sector coupling, distribution grid.
6. *FS6 - Digitalisation*: ICT penetration, smart metering, digital substations, smart building interface, validating ICT solutions, etc.

Initial Plans (First Round Questionnaire)

After asking to the partners which of the listed FSs do they relate their educational contribution to these were the results. FS1 was selected by 8 partners, FS6 was selected by 6 partners, FS4 was selected by 6 partners, FS2 was selected by 4 partners, FS3 was selected by 2 partners and FS5 was selected by 2 partners. The results are summarised in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Results of questionnaire about Functional Scenarios of relevance for the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium partners.

Analysis of Activity Plans

Moreover, in the quantification of the FSs covered by the training activities it is found that most of them are classified within the group FS6 as shown in Figure 6. For the case of FS5 and FS4, almost no training activity has been classified under these FSs. This may be explained by the fact that, for instance, there has not been carried out any activity in the topic of flexibility management.

Figure 6: Analysis of Functional Scenarios covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning so far.

2.2.2 Training Activity Topics and Focus Areas

The area of subjects covered by ERIGrid 2.0 is quite broad, so that it was helpful to break down the topics into more concrete areas of work. Initially, this break-down was performed in context of an internal survey. The identified topics can be defined as follows:

1. *Distributed Energy Resources (DERs)*: Refers to the modular energy generation (e.g., Photovoltaic (PV) solar, micro turbines, co-generation) and storage systems located at the end-user level that can operate to supply the local demand either partially or totally, as well as inject energy into the electrical grid (DNV-GL, 2014).
2. *Energy Storage Systems (ESSs)*: Stands for a scheme destined to take up an amount of energy and store in a specific way over a period of time in order to be used in another instance (Ausfelder, 2016).

3. *Distribution Management Systems and Distribution Network Operation*: This topic refers to management, operation and optimisation related concepts and tools implemented for the electrical network at a distribution level addressed to ensure its continuity.
4. *Ancillary Services by Distributed Generation (DG), Storage and Active Grid Assets*: Ancillary services are those actions and equipment in the generation, transmission or distribution sector with the purpose of supporting the base generation, ensuring the electrical network stability and, as a consequence, ensuring the energy supply to the end-consumer (Hirst & Kirby, 1996). This topic considers in particular the provision of ancillary services from non-conventional assets, including storage and distributed generation such as PV or wind power plants.
5. *Frequency and Voltage Stability*: Topic related to assess the electrical network stability in terms of voltage and frequency, i.e., the capacity of the grid for keeping these variables close to their nominal values at any moment. Thus, the impact of an event in can be assessed by analysing the stability repercussions.
6. *Microgrids*: Those are low voltage electrical networks which include diverse generation sources (either renewable and non-renewable), storage systems and controllable loads as a single scheme (Madureira et al., 2009).
7. *Multi-energy/carrier systems/sector coupling*: Multi-energy carriers stand for systems in which more than one way of energy is involved, e.g., electricity and thermal networks are combined as an integral scheme. This area can also compress coupling and different data exchange infrastructure between the energy sectors.
8. *Inverter Dominated Power Systems*: Inverter dominated networks stand for power systems in which most of the generation comes from inverter-based resources such as PV, wind instead of the traditional fossil-fuel based generation. Likewise, these systems include EV storage and High Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) schemes which have considerable relevance.
9. *ICT in Smart Grids*: ICT stands for the access to the information through telecommunication technologies, in this case, applied to smart grids-related topics. Among the technologies, internet, wireless networks and other similar are included (Ratheeswari, 2018).
10. *Demand Response*: This approach, in the field of electricity, is a denomination that encloses schemes in which the end-consumer varies its consumption pattern according to the variations on the electricity price imposed by the distribution system operator (Albadi & El-Saadany, 2007).
11. *Aggregation and Flexibility Management*: In the context of energy systems, the term 'flexibility' refers the management of demand response, i.e., injection and consumption interaction from the users as actors that aggregate resources to an electrical network with a distributed generation scheme (Eid, Codani, Chen, Perez, & Hakvoort, 2015).
12. *Energy communities*: They are an alternative collective governing scheme in energy systems in which the citizens determine the energy processes operation according to their social objectives in a democratic way (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).
13. *Digitisation of Energy Systems*: Digitisation process refers to the technological transformation in terms of digital advances of energy systems with the goal of optimising their operation, improving their reliability and modernising any other aspect related to them.
14. *Direct Current (DC) Power Systems*: Electricity network affairs operating with DC, rather

than the typical Alternating Current (AC) three-phase grids. Includes for example high-voltage DC transmission or DC Microgrids.

15. *Energy Market*: Is a regulated market oriented to the trade of energy either electrical or any other energy source (Mohammadi-Ivatloo, Shotorbani, & Anvari-Moghaddam, 2021). In this area includes any activity related to the energy trading and pricing.
16. *Other*: Any other training activity topic not included in the aforementioned categories.

The above topics were explicitly inquired in the first survey. In the context of the activity plans the mapping to the topics was done manually, based on the training activity description and training objectives.

Initial Plan (First Round Questionnaire)

The results of the initial survey are summarised in Figure 7. The results show a great interest on the following topics: DERs, Microgrids, ICT in Smart Grids, Energy Communities and Digitalisation of Energy Systems with six or more partners. On the contrary, the topics Energy Market, Multi-energy/carrier systems/sector coupling, DC Power Systems and Demand Response are the lowest covered by the partners. Also, an additional area was suggested by one partner in the topic “Simulation Infrastructure”.

Figure 7: Results of questionnaire about activity topics of relevance for the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium partners.

Analysis of Activity Plans

The activity plans included in this analyses include those already delivered or in planning status. It should be noted that the quantitative analysis is based on a qualitative (manual) interpretation of the reported activity plans.

The analysis gives insights about which topics from those initially listed in Section 2.1 are trending and which ones are vaguely covered until now. Once said, Figure 8 illustrates the results of the topics analysis for both the delivered and in planning training activities. Note that, e.g., in the case of the covered topics statistics, the sum of activities is higher than the actual

number of delivered and in planning ones since a single activity may cover different topics on its scope.

Figure 8: Analysis of topics covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning so far.

The results indicate that the by far most frequently represented topics are those related to *Distributed Energy Resources* and *Digitisation of Energy Systems*. Each of these two topics was covered by more than 10 activities, which sum up around half of the delivered activities. Other topics from the list which account for the remaining number of activities appear to a lesser extent. In contrast, four topics from the list have neither been covered by any activity so far nor are planned to be addressed in the short-term: *Inverter Dominated Power Systems*, *Demand Response*, *Aggregation and Flexibility Management*, and *Energy Markets*. This suggests that future activities to be promoted in ERIGrid 2.0 must be oriented to these four topics or areas as a priority.

2.2.3 Validation Methods

The following list of research tools and laboratory testbeds is interpreted as an escalation of validation methods that can assist in maturing technologies to a range of Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs)². The methods considered here allow a validation on the range between TRL3 and TRL6, in exceptional cases even TRL7:

1. *Simulation (Monolithic)*: Monolithic simulation allows validation of algorithms, e.g., against a benchmark simulation model, achieving a maturity of typically TRL3.
2. *Co-simulation*: The co-simulation tools enable the joint simulation of different domains, e.g., electricity system together with communication network or the coupling of standalone simulators of different time steps, for the performance of a joint simulation. The co-simulation platform takes care of the time synchronisation and the interactions across the sub-simulators. Co-simulation allows integration of original code components typi-

²https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

cally, and even permits interfacing of complete external components, the relevant maturity level can be higher than in pure simulation; TRL3 to TRL4.

3. C^3/P^4 HIL: HIL is an advanced laboratory testing method in which actual hardware components, like controllers, relays, loads, inverters, etc, are interfaced to a Digital Real Time Simulator (DRTS) for studying the behaviour of the Device Under Test (DUT) in a safe environment and conditions close to real, achieving typically a maturity in the range of TRL3 to TRL5
4. *Geographically Distributed Real Time Simulation (GDRTS) or Geographically Distributed Hardware-in-the-Loop (GDHIL)*: Geographically distributed real time simulations refer to the interconnection of two remote laboratories over the internet to realise experiments that harness the capabilities of the two laboratories. Depending on whether the interconnection is that of two digital real time simulators or include or HIL, the typical achieved maturity is in the range of TRL3 to TRL5.
5. *Coupling of Multiple Entities*: As here the coupling of mature software and hardware with simulated and physical infrastructure is possible, a level of TRL6 can be reached (e.g., non-real time simulator with real-time simulator).
6. *Other*: Validation methods which do not fit in the others categories such as optimisation or virtual laboratory, as well as those training activities which do not specify a validation method.

Initial Plans (First Round Questionnaire)

After asking to the partners which validation methods contemplated ERIGrid 2.0 they expected to implement for the educational activities, the results are shown in Figure 9. Distributed Real-time Simulation (RTS) or HIL was selected by 6 partners. Coupling of multiple entities was selected by 6 partners. C/P HIL was selected by 5 partners. Co-simulation was selected by 4 partners. Additionally, it was reported other two testing technologies: Virtual laboratories and Optimisation, whereas Simulation (Monolithic) was introduced later in the project, which means it did not appear in the initial questionnaire, and therefore no partners selected it.

Figure 9: Results of questionnaire about validation methods initially expected to be implemented in the ERIGrid 2.0 training activities. Note that “Simulation (Monolithic)” was added after the survey.

Analysis of Activity Plans

With respect to the analysis of the validation methods implemented during the training activities, it is found that all methods defined in early stages have been used so far. The results are illustrated in Figure 10. The most referred validation method is in the category “Others”, which

³Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL)

⁴Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL)

covers any other methodology not included in the list (e.g., virtual laboratory, optimisation) as well as those training activities which do not specify a validation method.

Figure 10: Analysis of validation methods covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project's training activities delivered and in planning (02/2023).

In contrast, the validation method least referred is the monolithic simulation. On the other hand, all the other categories have similar number of activities in which were referred as validation methods.

2.3 Learning Outcomes based on Target Audience and Training Objectives

The development of ERIGrid 2.0 ILOs is based on an understanding of the target audience and training objectives, i.e., the areas where the project aims to provide educational services.

This section will provide a reflection on the intended learning outcomes, which were included in the training activity plans, and can be associated with training objectives summarised in the previous section. In this way the reflection aims to provide guidance on the planning on further objectives to address the planned project outcomes.

2.3.1 Intended Learning Outcomes

ILOs can then be formulated as concrete capabilities a learner will be able to perform upon successful completion of a training activity. The formulation of concrete learning outcomes assists in the alignment and coordination of training activities' scopes and enables the systematic assessment of both learning outcomes and success of training modules developed.

Analysis of Intended Learning Outcomes

The characterisation of ILOs is based on the Bloom Taxonomy. According to Bloom Taxonomy, there are six levels of learning/understanding, which are defined as follows:

1. **Knowledge:** Involves recognising or remembering facts, terms, basic concepts, or answers without necessarily understanding their meaning; typical keywords are "memorise".
2. **Comprehension:** involves demonstrating an understanding of facts and ideas by organising, summarising, translating, generalising, giving descriptions, and stating the main ideas; typical keywords are "understand, explain, predict".
3. **Application:** Involves using acquired knowledge to solve problems in new situations. This involves applying acquired knowledge, facts, techniques and rules. Learners should be

able to use prior knowledge to solve problems, identify connections and relationships and how they apply in new situations. Typical keywords are “apply, show, illustrate”.

4. *Analysis*: Involves examining and breaking information into component parts, determining how the parts relate to one another, identifying motives or causes, making inferences, and finding evidence to support generalisations; typical keywords are “distinguish, solve, experiment”.
5. *Synthesis*: Involves building a structure or pattern from diverse elements; it also refers to the act of putting parts together to form a whole or bringing pieces of information together to form a new meaning. Typical keywords are “design, formulate, construct”.
6. *Evaluation*: Involves presenting and defending opinions by making judgements about information, the validity of ideas, or quality of work based on a set of criteria; typical keywords are “evaluate, estimate, assess, appraise”.

Figure 11 presents the categorisation of Bloom Levels in the areas covered by ERIGrid 2.0’s training activities.

Figure 11: Categorisation of Bloom Levels in the areas covered by the training activities of ERIGrid 2.0.

It can be easily observed that the areas of “Distributed Energy Resources” and “Digitisation of Energy Systems” attract the interest of most training activities. Moreover, the “Comprehension” level of Bloom Taxonomy is accomplished in seventeen (17) training objectives, just after the “Application” level which is satisfied in nineteen (19) training objectives.

A view of the categorisation of Bloom Levels with respect to validation methods and tools implemented in the training activities of ERIGrid 2.0 is found in Figure 12 .

The “Application” level is also dominant here, indicating the effectiveness of the training activities accomplished.

Figure 12: Categorisation of Bloom Levels in the validation methods and tools covered by ERIGrid 2.0 project.

2.4 Conclusion of Educational Strategy

Gaps appear to remain between the intended and the achieved coverage of research areas by the planned training activities. To highlight a few, topics of “Demand Response”, and “Flexibility Management”, as well as “Inverter Dominated Systems” have not yet been addressed.

An analysis of intended cognitive level of competence (using Bloom’s taxonomy) reveals that the training activities are mostly aimed at comprehension and application experiences, with a few exceptions also considering analysis and synthesis skills. Given the scope and available time for most training activities, this level is as expected.

In the remaining project period, an effort will be made to address the gaps between the intended and planned topic areas. With two training schools remaining, also the support more depth in the competence levels can be expected.

In a future revision of the educational strategy approach, care should be taken to analyse, and possibly reduce the number of topic areas early in the process, avoiding redundancies. Also, instead of the *original* “Blooms’s Taxonomy”, it could be appropriate to apply the *revised* version, of the taxonomy.

3 Training Activities

The executed on-site training activities are reported in this section. The order of presentation starts with “Training Schools for Researchers” in Section 3.1, then “Training of Students, Professionals, and the General Public” in Section 3.2, “Workshops and Seminars” in Section 3.3, and finally “Sessions Organised at International Conferences” in Section 3.4. The associated activity plans and reports are attached in Appendix A.2 and Appendix A.3.

3.1 Training Schools for Researchers

Training schools for researchers are targeted at PhD students and early stage researchers, aiming to equip them with knowledge and experience required to perform advanced research in the field. The purpose of these schools is to convey state-of-the-art and fundamental techniques, experience with research tools and laboratories, as well as relevant industrial applications. In addition to classic summer and winter schools, also a virtual training programme is considered. The following Table 1 provides an overview of the planned and organised Training Schools. A brief outline about them are provided in the sections below.

Table 1: Planned and organised Training Schools; the scope column refers to the project’s Functional Scenarios.

Title	Hosting Partner	Partners	Scope	Participants		Material
				Total	Internal	
Introduction to Real Time Digital Simulation with Applications in Sustainable Energy Systems (Jan. 2023)	TUD	ICCS, UoS	FS1, FS5	12	2	Materials, Report
Modern power systems operation and validation (Fall 2023)	ICCS	HEDNO, UCY	FS1, FS2, FS4	<i>planned</i>		—
Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems (Fall 2023)	AIT	—	FS6	<i>planned</i>		—
Sector coupling for Electricity and District Energy Systems (Winter 2023/24)	DTU	AIT, TUD	FS3, FS6	<i>planned</i>		—

3.1.1 Implemented Training Schools

Training School on “Introduction to Real Time Digital Simulation with Applications in Sustainable Energy Systems”

A training school on introduction to DRTS with applications in sustainable energy systems was organised by the Intelligent Electrical Power Grids (IEPG) section of the Electrical Sustainable Energy (ESE) department at the Delft University of Technology from January 23 to 26, 2023. The training school introduced participants to real-time power system simulations and its wide range of applications in sustainable energy systems. This included modelling and simulation of renewables such as wind turbines and high voltage DC applications. Furthermore, the training school also touched upon the concept of CHIL, in collaboration with the University of Strathclyde and National Technical University of Athens.

Summary of Activity

Day 1: The first day of the winter school focused on introduction to real-time power system simulations. An introductory lecture on overview of RTDS hardware and its associated software RSCAD was given. Following this, participants modelled and simulated a simple power system model on the RTDS.

Days 2 and 3: On days 2 and 3, theoretical lectures and hands-on simulations were carried out on the following topics:

- *Lecture:* Modelling of wind energy systems,
- *Lecture:* Introduction to small and sub time-step modelling of wind energy systems,
- *Hands-on:* Sub time-step modelling and simulation,
- *Lecture:* High-voltage DC and converters, and
- *Hands-on:* Modelling of high-voltage DC networks.

Day 4: On the final day of the training school, guest lectures on CHIL were provided by the University of Strathclyde and National Technical University of Athens to all participants. Furthermore, participants undertook a hands-on laboratory session on power system automation and protection using IEC 61850, to better understand HIL simulations.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

For the winter school, no final exam was conducted, nevertheless, the training school was well-received by all the visiting participants. Specifically, during discussions and breaks, the following aspects were much appreciated:

- Lecture content and exercise of Day 2 was well received. Particularly, attendees found the lab session and exercise highly engaging.
- The last day's lecture on CHIL and the demo exercise sparked a lot of interest in the participants. Furthermore, the lab visit allowed them to observe first-hand some of the concepts covered over the course of the winter school.

Photos from the Event

Photos from the winter school are shown in Figure 13.

3.1.2 Planned Training Schools

Training School on “Modern Power Systems Operation and Validation”

This school it is planned to take place in September 2023 in the National Technical University of Athens, Greece and will cover topics such as control, protection, ancillary services provided by DERs, HIL simulation and resilience of microgrids and smart grids, among others. The school will be organised by ICCS-NTUA, while HEDNO and UCY are potential co-organising partners. The school will be 4 or 5 days long, consisting of lectures, lab tour and hands-on laboratory demonstrations and sessions, while the last day, a visit to HEDNO's, Greece's Distribution System Operator (DSO)'s infrastructure, will take place. The intended audience will

(a) Lecture session

(b) Group photo with all participants

Figure 13: Photos from the winter school at TU Delft in Jan. 2023.

be students, researchers, and professionals in the area of modern power systems operation, validation and simulation, which are core areas of ERIGrid 2.0.

Training School on “Digitalisation of Smart Energy Systems”

Together with the linked Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Program (H2020) SINERGY project a virtual training course on the digitalisation of smart energy systems is planned.

Hosting location: virtual

Planned hosting period: December 2023

Training School on “Sector coupling for Electricity and District Energy Systems”

To accommodate an affordable renewable energy supply the energy system needs to become further integrated with access and flow of flexibility resources across several sectors. This

transition requires improved monitoring and more dynamic operation of the thermal energy systems of buildings and district heat networks. This summer school will introduce tools and methods to investigate sector coupling across electricity and district heat networks. Sector coupling solutions and use cases will be introduced, the relevant control and operational interactions described. The testing and validation of sector coupling use cases and solutions will be demonstrated using state of the art simulation tools, laboratory experiments and visits to the field sites.

Hosting location: Risø Campus, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark

Planned hosting period: March 2024

3.2 Training Events for Students, Professionals, and the Public

Dedicated events have been organised also for target groups outside the research spectrum, including High School Students (HSSs) and the General Public (GP) audience. An event for industry Professionals (P) is under planning and thus not yet reported here. The following Table 2 provides an overview of the planned and organised Training Events. A brief outline about them are provided in the sections below.

Table 2: Organised Training Events for High School Student, Professionals, and the General Public.

Title	Partner	Audience	Venue	Attendees	Date
Environmental education through the construction of a PV module	ICCS	HSS	Ekali, Greece	20	30/03, 7, 11/04/2022
Nuffield Research Placements at Strathclyde – Supporting Sustainable Aviation	UoS	HSS	UoS DSPL, Glasgow, UK	7	25/07-05/08/2022
European Researcher's Night (ERN) 2020	AIT	GP	virtual	>1,000	27/11/2020
European Researcher's Night (ERN) 2022	AIT	GP	Vienna, Austria	>1,000	30/09/2022

3.2.1 Environmental Education through the Construction of a PV Module

Summary of the Activity

The 3-day activity organised by ICCS-NTUA took place in the 1st Arsakeio Tositsio General High School of Ekali, in Athens, Greece. During the first 2-hour workshop on environmental and social issues caused by climate change the following topics were discussed: an introduction to climate change, the earth's energy balance, the greenhouse gasses and energy balance, the impacts on physical systems, the consequences of climate change & adaptation, the science consensus and the climate change debate, and mitigation strategies. During the second 2-hour workshop, renewable energy technologies were presented as a solution to climate change issues and energy equality and access. Wind and solar energy have been explained with the presentation of wind turbines and solar modules. Large scale application of these technologies, such as solar parks and wind farms were presented and community energy initiatives around Europe were explained. Further on, the United Nations (UN) 'Sustainable Energy for All' global initiative⁵ for universal energy access, improvement of energy efficiency, and increase of the

⁵<https://www.seforall.org/>

use of renewable energy, was explained, with a global perspective on energy equality. Examples of electrification case studies in rural Africa were presented from the SmartRue research group.

During the two 4-hour 'Engineering in Practice' workshops, the high school students had a unique opportunity to engage with a renewable energy technology, such as photovoltaic electricity, with a practical hands-on experience. Initially, they were exposed to information on the photovoltaic phenomenon and its application on solar modules, along with background information and off-grid and grid-tied renewable energy systems. Simple circuit diagrams were drawn up by the students in order to design the solar panel to be constructed for charging a 12V battery. This is a simple engineering task that provides the students with an appreciation of the principles of engineering in practice. Once the amount of solar cells and the connection setup required were decided, the students had a chance to construct the module with simple tools and materials. Gender equality associated with manual work was addressed throughout the construction process making sure both male and female students participated equally. While the construction was carried out, all aspects of solar module manufacturing were discussed and explained, such as the thickness of the glass surface, the importance of keeping the construction clean and avoiding particles to reside on the solar cells, etc. This created a conceptual link between the manual process that the students experience and the actual activities in an industrial solar module manufacturing facility. Once the construction was completed, the students performed electrical experiments on the module, testing it for open circuit voltage, short circuit current and calculating the power produced once connected to a 12V battery. The optimum inclination of the solar module was found experimentally and the importance of orientation and inclination of solar panels was discussed. The actual act of implementing a solar panel design that the students have made creates a direct association between engineering design and engineering products in use.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The ERIGrid 2.0 high school activity promoted aspects of experiential learning which is a way of learning that supports students in applying their knowledge and conceptual understanding to real-world problems. The target audience was high school students and the total number of participants were 20. The students familiarized themselves with topics like renewable energy and climate change and were given the opportunity to learn in a real-life practical situation by constructing a solar panel. The students deepened their knowledge through repeatedly acting and then reflecting on the action and developed skills through practice. Finally, skills and qualities were acquired while working in groups and while manipulating tools and equipment.

3.2.2 Nuffield Research Placements at Strathclyde – Supporting Sustainable Aviation

Summary of the Activity

The decarbonisation of aviation towards net-zero emissions flight is an important step towards Governments' ambition to realise a net-zero future. Immediate action towards the electrification and hydrogenation of aircraft is necessary to support ambition. While research is carried out at the University of Strathclyde supporting various aspects of the ambition, at the same time it is necessary to educate and motivate pupils about the exciting challenges we address on a daily basis. Three internships for high school students in Year 12 to work on projects related

to Sustainable Aviation were offered at the [Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory](#) at UoS in collaboration with [Nuffield Research Placements](#).

During the two-week internship, these students were able to appreciate the experimental methods currently under development at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory for the characterisation of arc faults within aero-electrical power systems. These experimental methods support the overarching agenda of ERIGrid 2.0 in accelerating the validation and deployment of novel technologies. Firstly, the concept of sustainable aviation and the research and development of electrification of aircraft and its associated challenges were introduced to the pupils. Furthermore, accompanied by the physical lab demonstration of the DC series arc phenomena through an experimental rig, the pupils were informed of the state-of-the-art research experimental research undertaken at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory to address the challenges that arise from DC series arcs. In addition, to facilitate the pupils with preliminary research skills, elementary critical literature reviews on the more electric aircraft aided sustainable aviation and DC series arc characterisation have been undertaken by the pupils. At the final stage of the internship, the pupils carried out the hands-on experimental analysis of the datasets and samples obtained through the experiments to appreciate the damage to the surroundings due to an arc event.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

During this internship, the concept of Sustainable Aviation along with the research and development of aircraft electrification has been demonstrated to high-school students. Through this experience, we were able to expand their knowledge base and broaden their horizons, as well as ignite their interest and motivation for further exploration of this research area. In addition, the pupils were given the opportunity to get involved in real-world DC arc experiments, which enabled them to develop their perspectives and skills in experimental validation and data analysis. These acquired skills enable the pupils to apply their prior knowledge and conceptual understanding into practice. Furthermore, the knowledge and skills acquired by the pupils during this internship not only support the student's academic pursuits, but also better prepare them for their undergraduate studies.

3.2.3 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action “European Researcher’s Nights”

Summary of the Activity

The ERNs – a Marie Skłodowska-Curie Action of the European Commission (EC)⁶ – takes place every year simultaneously in several hundred cities all over Europe and beyond. The key objective of the event is to increase GP awareness of the diversity of scientific research and also to promote and facilitate greater public participation in the entire scientific process. One of the further goals of the event is to enhance youth's understanding of science and research and encourage them to pursue a career in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM).

ERIGrid 2.0 has participated in the ERNs in 2020 and 2022, represented by AIT in Vienna, Austria. Due to the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic, the 2020 edition was carried out virtually; ERIGrid 2.0 was represented with a talk introducing smart grids in general as well as its development and validation⁷.

⁶<https://marie-sklodowska-curie-actions.ec.europa.eu/>

⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4294213>

In 2022, ERIGrid 2.0 contributed to the Austrian event (i.e., Viennese part) called “exploRE-search” on September 30. The programme of this event included various engaging activities ranging from interdisciplinary science booths, workshops, and the dedicated European Union (EU) corner to science slam sessions, and science cafes.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The target audience for ERIGrid 2.0 at the ERNs in 2020 and 2022 was the GP as well as potential stakeholders. Reaching those interested persons in 2020 was rather difficult due to the virtual character of the event. In the end, there were not much discussions or feedback after the above outlined talk.

The situation in 2022 was better, since a significant amount of persons visited the joint booth of H2020 ERIGrid 2.0 and HYPERRIDE⁸. Different aspects of smart grids and related developments have been introduced and disseminated to the GP during the ERN 2022. Also, recent outcomes and achievements of ERIGrid 2.0 have been presented.

Impressions from the ERIGrid 2.0 participation at the ERN 2020 are provided in Figure 14.

Figure 14: ERIGrid 2.0 at the European Researcher's Night 2022 in Vienna, Austria.

⁸<https://hyperride.eu>

3.3 Workshops and Seminars

Workshops and Seminars are on-site events organised separately from a conference, and typically target researchers from academia and industry at all levels. The following Table 3 provides an overview of the organised events, whereas a brief outline about them are provided in the sections below.

Table 3: Overview of organised Workshops and Seminars.

Title	Partner	Venue	Attendees	Material	Date
Supporting a glocal energy transition: from local energy communities to global simulation networks	JRC	JRC, Ispra, Italy	47	Materials	9-10/11/2022
EU ERIGrid 2.0 and NSF IRES US-PRISM Joint Workshop	UoS, TUD, ICCS	TUD, Delft, Netherlands	7	see Report	15/07/2022
ICT for automation in smart grid and its cybersecurity challenges	SINTEF	SINTEF, Trondheim, Norway	31	Materials	30-31/01/2023
Overview of the EU Horizon 2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project	ICCS, UoS	IIT Bhubaneswar, India	n/a	n/a	16/02/2023

3.3.1 Supporting a Glocal Energy Transition: From Local Energy Communities to Global Simulation Networks

Summary of the Activity

The 2-day workshop, organised in collaboration with Politecnico di Torino, RWTH Aachen and the Ensiel consortium of Italian universities, disseminated the research activities of the JRC Smart Grid Interoperability Laboratory, fostering the community discourse on the topics of renewable energy communities and global simulation networks. The event saw the participation of distinguished international speakers from academia, industry and public institutions, which have discussed these subjects in the wider context of the energy transition. The audience included Stakeholders of the energy sectors (researchers, industry, regulators). The first day of the event focused on energy communities, presenting some of the latest success stories in the field and discussing their role in the future decarbonised power system under a rapidly changing regulatory framework. This session saw the participation of the Comunità Energetica di Magliano Alpi, which presented the results of its laboratory access activity in the Smart Grid Interoperability Laboratory (JRC Ispra) in the context of the TA2 work package. The second day of the seminar focused on the internet-of-labs paradigm, discussing its impact in supporting the energy transition and showcasing a real-time demonstrative experiment with the joint participation of six European laboratories. The experiment and the subsequent discussions were particularly relevant to the “Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools” in ERIGrid 2.0.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

On the first day, the workshop participants familiarised themselves with Renewable Energy Communities. The presentations and discussions focused in particular on regulatory objec-

tives and challenges, technological and social developments, and the role of energy communities in driving the energy transition. During the second day of the workshop, a live multi-site laboratory experiment showcased the capabilities of Geographically-Distributed Real-Time Simulations and demonstrated their potential role in supporting the design and operation of decarbonised energy systems.

3.3.2 EU ERIGrid 2.0 and NSF IRES USPRISM Joint Workshop

Summary of the Activity

The half-day joint workshop was organized by UoS and NSF IRES USPRISM programme and was hosted by TUD, in the Netherlands. Co-organizers of the event were ICCS-NTUA and TUD. It was comprised of six presentations in two main areas; advances in testing methods for power systems validation and laboratory testing for the promotion of aircrafts electrification. Initially, two speakers from UoS and ICCS-NTUA discussed the transformation of power grids and how it can be tackled through the advances in laboratory testing methods. The HIL and GDRTS methods were presented, as well as examples, testbeds and results from realised experiments. More specifically, the HIL testing of a PV power plant controller according to the latest EU RfG code was presented, as well as a GDRTS example for the study of frequency control of UK's transmission network. Next, the four speakers from the NSF IRES USPRISM programme presented their research subjects. In more detail, the first speaker discussed the experimental characterisation of airflow impact on DC series electrical arc faults for aircraft applications, while explained the motivation behind his research topic and the correlation to the energy transition. The following speaker, talked about the use of new material is used in aviation and the importance of studying their electrical properties. He also presented his work in the designing and testing a sensor that measures compression force applied to the sample. The next speaker explained how the live grid data can be used for power system validation and made a live demonstration of the developed tool for that purpose. The last speaker, presented a newly developed neural network-based control scheme for power converters. After the presentations, a half-an-hour discussion took place between the speakers for knowledge exchange and brainstorming on future research directions. A lab tour to the ESP and RTDS laboratories of TUD concluded the workshop.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The ERIGrid 2.0 and NSF IRES USPRISM joint workshop enabled the knowledge exchange and the promotion of research and research-related activities between ERIGrid 2.0 partners and U.S. science and engineering students, on topics related to validation of power and energy systems. The target groups were undergraduate and post-graduate students and young researchers. There were 7 participants, and among them 4 were external to the ERIGrid 2.0 project (from universities). All the participants, in particular those external to ERIGrid 2.0, familiarise themselves with the scope of ERIGrid 2.0 project, the project partner's current research activities, advancements and methodologies. In addition, the participants had the possibility to engage in the knowledge exchange session to further discuss and share experiences on the specified laboratory validation related research activities. Last but not least, the participants had the chance to visit the modern research infrastructure of TUD university.

3.3.3 ICT for Automation in Smart Grid and its Cybersecurity Challenges

Summary of the Activity

The workshop was organised and hosted by SINTEF Energy, in collaboration with a research centre for intelligent distribution networks in Norway (CINELDI) and ERIGrid 2.0 partners (VTT, OFFIS, TUD, and DTU). It comprised 3 main sessions in three main focus areas; automation, the use of 5G and cyber security in smart grid. Each session had a keynote speech and a number of presentations from ERIGrid 2.0 and CINELDI partners. The presentations focused on sharing current research activities, experiences and the testbeds used in relation to the use of ICT for automation and the related cyber security challenges. In addition, the workshop saw participation of distinguished professionals and researchers from the industry (Statnett – a TSO in Norway), vendors (ABB) and academia (NTNU) as a keynote speaker for each of the three sessions. The first day of the workshop focused on the role and impact of ICT in the automation of the power grid. At the end of the first session, there was also a laboratory visit and demonstration in the National Smart Grid Laboratory of SINTEF. The second day focused on cyber security in the automation of the grid, in particular on the methods, techniques and testbeds employed in studying cybersecurity issues in smart grid.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The workshop enabled ERIGrid 2.0 partners to share knowledge and research experience in the areas of automation and cybersecurity in smart grid. The target groups were researchers and professionals from both academia and industry. There were close to 31 participants, and among them 21 were external to the ERIGrid 2.0 project (mainly from grid operators and universities). All the participants, in particular those external to ERIGrid 2.0, familiarise themselves with the scope of ERIGrid 2.0 project, the project partner's current research activities including the test-beds being developed in the areas of grid automation and its cybersecurity challenges. In addition, the participants had the possibility to engage in the Q&A sessions to further discuss and share experiences on the specified ICT related research activities.

3.3.4 Overview of the EU Horizon 2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project – Working Towards Development of Tools and Methods for Validation of Complex Power and Energy Systems

Summary of the Activity

A set of presentations delivered at the IEEE PELS IIT BBS Student Chapter event: “Control, stability and testing of inverter-based power systems and microgrids” at Bhubaneswar, India. The 2-day event was jointly organized by the RE-EMPOWERED and ERIGrid 2.0 H2020 projects. In the first day, the researchers from ICCS-NTUA presented their research work as part of the two projects. In the second day, three presentations were delivered, by ICCS-NTUA and UoS; The first speaker gave an introduction to the transformation of the grid and explained the importance of the trusted validation of complex power and energy systems. The second speaker presented the educational developments of ERIGrid 2.0 and the available resource centre in the ERIGrid 2.0 webpage where the potential users have open access to those. The third speaker presented the TA/VA possibilities that the ERIGrid 2.0 offers and an example of successful implementation of laboratory access.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The present seminar introduced the participants into the topic of validation of smart energy systems, as well as highlighted recent advances in the control, stability, and testing of inverter-based power systems and microgrids. It is noteworthy that following to the technical presentations, interesting discussions took place between the presenters and the participants. Last but not least, this seminar showcased the capabilities that ERIGrid 2.0 projects provides to practitioners in the field, both through its Virtual Access and Transnational Access activities.

3.4 Sessions at Conferences

An overview of organised sessions and activities at scientific conferences and events is provided in Table 4, whereas a brief summary of them is provided in the following sections.

Table 4: Overview of organised tutorials, special and panel sessions.

Title	Type ^a	Partner	Conference	Attendees	Date
Real-time simulation advancing education and training on power and energy systems	PS	ICCS	IEEE PES General Meeting 2021	n/a	27/07/2021
Coordinated Control and Co-Simulation of Power Systems in Energy Internet	PS	UoS	IEEE PES General Meeting 2022	30	18/07/2022
Validating Smart Energy Systems	T	AIT	IEEE SMC 2022	5	09/10/2022
Pushing the Boundaries of Real-Time Simulations for Validation of Future Complex Power Systems	PS	UoS, AIT, ICCS	IEEE ISGT Europe 2022	28	11/10/2022

^aTutorial (T), Special Session (SS), and Panel Session (PS)

3.4.1 Tutorials

Tutorial “Validating Smart Energy Systems” at IEEE SMC 2022

Summary of the Activity

A driving force for the realisation of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technological developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and market liberalisation, the system’s operation needs adaptation. Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a smart grid. While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments and testing will play a significantly larger role in realising future solutions and technologies. Proper validation approaches, concepts, and tools are partly missing until now.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing validation methods and tools for validating smart energy systems which are currently being developed in the European project ERIGrid 2.0.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

This tutorial addressed training needs related to system-level validation and testing, especially for researchers/academics and engineers that are active in the domain of power and energy systems. The aforementioned stakeholders were educated on (i) validation and testing approaches and (ii) methods and tools based on selected examples. Moreover, a brief introduction to smart energy systems, as well as the ERIGrid 2.0 approach, was also made.

3.4.2 Special and Panel Sessions

Panel Session “Real-time simulation advancing education and training on power and energy systems” at IEEE PES General Meeting 2021

Summary of the Activity

This panel session, organised by ICCS-NTUA as a joint activity of IEEE PES Task Force on Innovative Teaching Methods for Modern Power and Energy Systems and ERIGrid 2.0 project. The panel session comprised 5 main presentations covering the following topics: (i) Exploring new interactive teaching methods thanks to real time simulation, (ii) Real-time cyber-power testbed for training and education, (iii) Industry training using HIL simulation of replica control and protection panels for HVDC systems, (iv) Real-time Simulations and HIL as an effective tool in post-graduate power engineering education, (v) HIL simulation for hands-on experiential laboratory education on modern power systems. All presentations in this panel session were dedicated to showcase the importance of using HIL simulation for educational/training purposes on energy topics in both academia and industry. Through this panel session, the breakthroughs, the developments and advancements in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0 project and experiences of the Task Force members have been disseminated to the intended audiences.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

This panel session showcased the importance of using new and advanced educational and training tools for tackling the challenges associated with DER integration to promote the energy transition. Moreover, shed light on the potential of using real-time HIL simulation for educational/training purposes on energy topics in both academia and industry. Examples and reference experiences were shared for distinct applications, such as power system protection, power electronics, DER integration and smart grids.

Panel Session “Coordinated Control and Co-Simulation of Power Systems in Energy Internet” at IEEE PES General Meeting 2022

Summary of the Activity

This panel session, organised by UoS, comprised 5 main invited presentations covering the following topics: (i) Complex Power and Energy Systems Validation through interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories, (ii) Distributed Control and Optimisation in Power Systems, (iii) Real-Time Hybrid Co-Simulation for Large-Scale Power System using RTDS and TSAT, (iv) Data-Driven Coordinated Control of Networked-Microgrid Systems, (v) Introduction to TF: Cloud-Based Control and Co-Simulation of Multi-party Resources in Energy Internet. All presentations in this panel session were dedicated to showcasing the application of the novel real-time simulation and geographically distributed co-simulation techniques to the validation of complex power systems and the cloud-based coordinated control in energy

internet. The objective of these presentations also involves disseminating the advancements that enable the real-time co-simulation validation methodology being applied to the validation of novel coordinated control in modern power systems. The reported developments are the key enabler for applying the novel coordinated control to complex power systems through cloud-based co-simulation techniques. These are essential to offer both academic researchers and industrial practitioners who are interested in the geographically distributed real-time simulation and cloud-based power system coordinated control with the most recent research advancements and stimulate new pathways for further research and development. Through this panel session, the breakthroughs, developments, and advancements achieved related to of the ERIGRID 2.0 project have been disseminated to the intended audiences.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

This panel session provided a forum for academic researchers and industrial practitioners to exchange knowledge and share research experiences on innovative real-time co-simulation techniques aimed at validating coordinated control techniques for complex power systems. The research advancements on the emerging geographically distributed real-time co-simulation techniques that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of the cloud-aided coordinated control schemes have been disseminated to the intended audiences who are interested in real-time simulation and expertise in the power system design and control. Moreover, through disseminating the breakthroughs, developments, and advancements achieved related to the “Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools” developments of the ERIGRID 2.0 project, the participants acquired a more in-depth understanding of the ongoing research activities of the ERIGRID project and familiarised themselves with the scopes of ERIGRID project. This, in turn, stimulated new collaborative research activities using the ERIGRID 2.0 access program between UoS and other research institutes.

Panel Session “Pushing the Boundaries of Real-Time Simulations for Validation of Future Complex Power Systems” at IEEE ISGT Europe 2022

Summary of the Activity

This panel session, organized by UoS in collaboration with ICCS-NTUA and AIT, comprised 4 main invited presentations covering the following topics: (i) Shaping Future Power Systems with Real-Time Simulation, (ii) Interface Algorithms for Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation: Addressing the Stability and Accuracy Constraints, (iii) Ultra High-Fidelity Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulations for Microgrids and Electrical Distribution Networks, (iv) Experiences with Next Generation Validation Methods for the Derisking of the Renewable Dominated Grids: Black-Start. All of these presentations focused on the novel real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems, disseminating the advancements that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of future grid solutions. The reported developments are the key enabler for more robust power hardware-in-the-loop simulation setups with high fidelity over extended operating constraints. These are essential to provide both academic researchers and industrial practitioners who are interested in the hardware-in-the-loop simulation and geographically distributed real-time simulation with the most recent research advancements, and stimulating new pathways for further research and collaborations. Through this panel session, the breakthroughs and the developments and advancements achieved related to the “Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools” developments of the ERIGRID 2.0 project have been disseminated to the intended audiences.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

This panel session facilitated a knowledge-sharing and research-experience exchange environment among the ERIGrid partners on innovative real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems. The advancements that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of future grid solutions have been disseminated to the intended audiences who are interested in the hardware-in-the-loop simulation and geographically distributed real-time simulation. In addition, through disseminating the breakthroughs and the developments and advancements achieved related to the “Improved and Extended Real-Time/Co-simulation and HIL Tools” developments of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, the participants including academic researchers and industrial practitioners acquired a more in-depth understanding of the ongoing research activities of the ERIGrid 2.0 project and familiarised themselves with the scopes of ERIGrid 2.0 project.

4 Overview Staff Exchange and Achievements

4.1 Principles and Method of Staff Exchange

4.1.1 Overview, Motivation, and Scope

The basic idea of the ERIGrid 2.0 staff exchange is already outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), Description of Action (DoA), as follows (*ERIGrid 2.0 Grant Agreement*, 2019):

The exchange of experiences and views between different project partners will be fostered in the framework of staff exchange. The exchanges are expected to support the work performed in the Networking Activities (NAs) and Joint Research Activities (JRAs). This task will define the administrative and legal procedures, as well as the financial aspects for effective staff exchange. It will facilitate the interested staff, sending institution and host institution, monitor the process and report the main outcomes after the end of each exchange.

Based on that outline, during the project starting phase the scope of the staff exchange has been refined according to the following points:

- Enables the exchange of experiences and views between different partners,
- Excellent possibility for joint work between partners,
- Possibility for project partners to collaborate on common topics, interests, and joint activities,
- Supports the work performed in the NA and JRA Work Packages (WPs), and
- Staff exchange is personal-related (i.e., linked to a specific person).

4.1.2 Basic Principles, Procedure, and Evaluation Criteria

For the implementation of the staff exchange during the project's lifetime the following basic principles have been defined:

- 20k EUR budget in total available (might be extended in the future if there is a budget left open due to COVID-19 restrictions), budget is handled by AIT,
- Continuous submission (no calls) and evaluation (from May 2022 until June 2024),
- Submission of a mini proposal via Application Form (details see Section 4.1.3),
- Evaluation of proposals by NA3.4 task members (i.e., AIT, CRES, HEDNO, and ICCS) in a short time,
- Max. 1-2 weeks of stay period and max. of 2k EUR travel and accommodation support per exchange (i.e., per person; no personal costs are covered); potential longer stays might be possible but related additional costs need to be covered by the corresponding person's home institution,
- Several submissions from one person are in principle possible (but not preferred),
- Joint exchange of a group of persons is possible but every person needs to submit an own Application Form (where the concrete work of a person needs to be described),

- Minimal reporting obligations (i.e., summary report + cost reimbursement sheet); reports (summary+ cost reimbursement) need to be sent not later than 14 days after the end of the stay to mgt@erigrd2.eu (details see Section 4.1.3),
- The content of the staff exchange must be strongly related to the ERIGrid 2.0 project objectives and topics (i.e., the exchange should support the implementation of the project according to the workplan), and
- The staff exchange takes place under the umbrella of the ERIGrid 2.0 (i.e., all obligations and duties of the GA and Consortium Agreement (CA) remain valid; no separate contract is necessary).

To realize a specific staff exchange the following steps apply:

1. Request permission from the host organization about the planned stay,
2. Submit the Application Form (details see Section 4.1.3) at least 2-3 weeks before the planned exchange will take place (please keep in mind that the evaluation of the application may need some days),
3. Organize the staff exchange after the application has been approved (i.e., book flight(s) and accommodation, interact with the host organization about administrative and technical details),
4. Execute the exchange (if possible, document your exchange with photos that can be included in the summary report),
5. Submit the following documents to mgt@erigrd2.eu (details see Section 4.1.3), and
 - Summary Report (one single document in pdf format), and
 - Signed Cost Reimbursement Sheet incl. travel and accommodation invoices, boarding cards, etc. ordered as listed in the cost sheet (one document in pdf format).
6. After the report and the cost reimbursement have been approved by AIT and the costs have been reimbursed, please confirm the money transfer with the corresponding Payment Receipt to mgt@erigrd2.eu.

For the evaluation of a specific staff exchange application the following two points are taken into account:

- Exchange content in line with project objectives and activities, and
- Overall costs and duration,

4.1.3 Documents and Forms

The following documents are being used in order to implement the different steps (submission, evaluation, realisation, and reporting) of a specific staff exchange:

- Application Form,
- Summary Report Template,
- Cost Reimbursement Sheet Template, and
- Payment Receipt Template.

Appendix B.1 provides details about those documents.

4.2 Staff Exchange Activities

The following sections provide an overview of the realised staff exchanges during the project's first 36 months, including a short summary of the exchanges.

4.2.1 Overview of Realised Staff Exchanges

Since the project start 12 staff exchange applications have been received and all of them were accepted for realisation. Table 5 provides an overview of them.

Table 5: Overview of the realised staff exchanges.

No	Name	Host	Sender	Period	Nature ^a	Researcher
1	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation	ICCS	UoS	23/06-30/06/2022	G	A. Paspatis
2	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation	ICCS	UoS	23/06-30/06/2022	G	A. Kontou
3	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	RWTH	12/12-14/12/2022	G	S. Vogel
4	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	AIT	12/12-14/12/2022	G	E. Widl
5	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	DTU	12/12-14/12/2022	G	O. Gehrke
6	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	RSE	12/12-14/12/2022	G	G. Paludetto
7	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	CRES	12/12-14/12/2022	G	J. Nikolettatos
8	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	OFFIS	12/12-14/12/2022	G	P. Das
9	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	VTT	12/12-14/12/2022	G	M. Opas
10	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	CEA	12/12-14/12/2022	G	P.M. Cong
11	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	CEA	12/12-14/12/2022	G	L.M. Tri
12	JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing	TUD	TEC	12/12-14/12/2022	G	J.A. López

^aIndividual Staff Exchange (I), Group Staff Exchange (G)

4.2.2 Summary of Realised Staff Exchanges

Staff Exchange “Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation”

Summary of the Activity

ICCS, UoS, and CEA have developed as part of JRA2 a novel Interface Algorithm (IA) for PHIL simulations that improve stability and accuracy, two important metrics for utilising PHIL simulations. PHIL has proven to be an advanced method for the validation of smart grid technologies

in a controlled laboratory environment, howbeit the testing is under conditions pretty close to actual field testing.

The developed interface algorithm, called Virtual Shifting Impedance (VSI) builds on proven existing algorithms, and virtually introduces a shifting impedance into the coupling topology of the DRTS and the Hardware under Test (HUT), through the controller of the amplifier. This IA, lends the characteristics and properties of the Physical Shifting Impedance (PSI) method, as well as the virtual impedance technique that in principle provides additional damping to a system. The VSI expands the applicability of PSI and the limitations of this method, which concerns the availability of variable hardware impedances at hand. Thus, the shifting part of the impedance can be virtually introduced in the controller of an amplifier, eliminating the need for hardware availability.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

The main purpose of the staff exchange was to validate the stability and accuracy properties of this method through simulations and experiments. The widely applicable feedback filter method was considered as the baseline scenario for the comparison. Moreover, using a delay compensation method was considered, to test if accuracy can be further improved. Furthermore, the experiments are related to the demonstrations to be implemented later in the project. Ultimately, a publication is currently in progress.

The related summary report of this group staff exchange is provided in Appendix B.2.1.

Staff Exchange “JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing”

Summary of the Activity

The JRA3-related staff exchange was aimed at further development and release of the Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI) v2.0 developed within the scope of the JRA3 middleware. The uAPI forms the basis for the lab middleware and data exchange service to be further used in the JRA4 demos. The major purposes of the staff exchange were as follows:

1. Update uAPI with changes as documented in GitHub⁹,
2. Implement uAPI v2.0 in transports tools: RWTH VILLAS¹⁰, ERIGrid JanDER¹¹, and AIT Lablink¹², and
3. Test the new version of the uAPI.

Achievements and Learning Outcomes

As previously mentioned, the main goals of the staff exchange were to update the uAPI to v2.0. Furthermore, the next goal was to implement its support in the most commonly used lab-coupling tools, within the ERIGrid 2.0 context, i.e., VILLAS, JanDER, and Lablink. Both these tasks have been successfully achieved post the staff exchange. The figure highlights the landing webpage for the documentation of the uAPI, keeping in line with the openAPI specification. The uAPI is summarized as a “Common API used by ERIGrid 2.0 research infrastructures to exchange signals for geographically distributed experiments.” Furthermore, two of the data-

⁹<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA-3.1-api>

¹⁰<https://github.com/VILLASframework>

¹¹<https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA-3.1-JaNDER-API>

¹²<https://github.com/ait-lablink>

exchange tools/transports have already implemented v2.0 of the uAPI – RWTH VILLAS and AIT Lablink.

The related summary report of this group staff exchange is provided in Appendix B.2.2.

5 Conclusions

This document reported on a range of training and coordination activities that together helped advance the state of shared knowledge of a broad range of target audiences in the research fields of ERIGrid 2.0.

An educational strategy was developed and presented here as method to allow a quantitative summative assessment of both, the types of activities, the content and scope, as well as the level of competences achieved by the training. This method was chosen to enable a bottom up creative development of activities and content, while still enabling a steering and coordination of the topics, content, competence levels and target groups.

The method includes a definition of research topics and validation methods and the quantitative assessment is made possible through interpretation of detailed activity plans provided by the training activity developers. The method was used to present an intermediate snapshot of the portfolio of training activities. By comparison with data from an initial survey, it thereby provided a gap assessment and feedback for the further planning of training activities.

The organisation and content of the ERIGrid 2.0 staff exchange was described. In total two group staff exchanges were executed, involving twelve members of ERIGrid 2.0 staff. As reported, these knowledge exchange activities significantly enhanced the common understanding of key technologies developed in the project.

As this report is an intermediate release, the results of the gap analysis provide guidance to the selection and prioritisation of further training activities. Training activities and staff exchange activities continue to be developed, and the final set of activities will be reported in an updated document of this report.

A method of feedback collection from participants in training activities should be developed and applied in the remaining activities; in particular those training events that are hosted by project partners and require registration of participants, such as the training schools and workshops.

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Appendix A: Activity Plans and Reports

A.1 Plan and Report Templates

A.1.1 Activity Plan Template

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

<Title>

Overview

Hosting partner:

Co-organizing partners:

Planned date: E.g. Summer '99 (as specific as possible)

Type of Activity:

Contact: Name, email address of person(s) filling in this form

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

Target group(s)

Which are the target groups meant to participate and benefit from this training activity? As specific as possible (e.g. utility, suppliers, technical staff, consultants, high-school students, general public, etc.)

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

As Training Objectives describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective. For "Workshops & Seminars" and "Panel Sessions" this section is optional.

This module intends to ...

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as "Intended Learning Objectives" – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom's revised taxonomy to describe the school's objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

A student who completed this course is able to:

1. e.g. Produce a coherent test description for a HIL experiment
2. ...

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organizers (NA3-Training_Activity_Report_Form)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Appendix 1: Formulating Learning objectives & Blooms Taxonomy
(to be deleted after completing)

The following illustration is helpful when formulating learning objectives for the Training Schools¹.

¹ Blooms taxonomy is often illustrated in levels where "Knowledge" is the most basic, followed by comprehension (against the clock in below illustration; note that in the 'Bloom's revised axonomy' the "synthesis" level has been replaced by "creating", which then was ascribed the highest level).

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.1.2 Activity Report Template

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report <Title>

Overview

Hosting partner:

Co-organizing partners:

Delivered date:

Type of Activity: *select one of:* Workshops or Seminars (including virtual interactive workshops); Training Schools (Fill-in the additional fields!); Tutorials (e.g. in context of a conference); Special sessions and Panel Sessions; Training of Professionals; Training of High School Students

Contact: Name, email address of person(s) filling in this form

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Provide the agenda and/or schedule of the event. (The schedule mostly applies to summer/winter schools and workshops)

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Provide the list of participants.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Provide information about the educational event, description of each presented topic, whether it was related to an ERIGrid 2.0 workpackage, etc.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Describe the main achievements and outcomes of the event (e.g. the participants familiarized themselves with topic A, etc.)

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

Provide statistics (No. Registered persons, No. of Attended Persons, No. of Project External Persons).

- A. *Insert a picture of the event video on YouTube or any other public repository (e.g. Zenodo)*
- B. *Insert photos of the event*

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

In case a questionnaire was distributed to participants, please provide the results.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2 Activity Plans

A.2.1 Environmental Education through the Construction of a PV Module

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Environmental Education and Renewable Energy Technologies for High Schools

Overview

Hosting partner: 1st Arsakeio Tositsio General High School of Ekali

Co-organizing partners: SmartRUE, School of the Earth

Planned date: April 2022

Type of Activity: Environmental Education in High Schools

Contact: Kostas Latoufis, latoufis@power.ece.ntua.gr

Short Description

Theoretical and practical environmental education projects in high schools aim to inform and mobilize students on the current issues of climate change and renewable energy sources. The project itself consists of one 2-hour workshop with the high school students, during which the environmental and social issues caused by climate change are analyzed and renewable energy technologies are presented, with the use of presentations, discussions and interactive games. This action is followed by another two 4-hour workshops during which the students construct a 45W polycrystalline solar panel using simple tools and materials. As ERIGrid 2.0 aims to foster system-level support and education for industrial and academic researchers in power and energy systems research and technology development, such actions aim at expanding the applied research nature of the project to the younger generation, while also informing on current ecological, technical and social issues.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

With a looming climate crisis, it is of crucial importance to increase environmental literacy and renewable energy awareness, especially in the high school environment. Environmental education in high schools has been evolving in the last decades in Greece, and currently there is an environmental education project in the curriculum for each year of high school. These projects mostly emphasize applied physics and are oriented towards laboratory experiments, and it is with this part of the high school curriculum that these actions are linked.

Target group(s)

High-school students

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

The main training objective of the action is experiential learning, a way of learning that supports students in applying their knowledge and conceptual understanding to real-world problems. The classroom can serve as a setting for experiential learning through practical activities such as case and problem-based studies, experiments, etc. However, when students are given opportunities to learn in real-life situations in the school or in the community, like those provided by practical applications and service-learning projects, the learning becomes significantly more powerful. By engaging in real-world experiences, students can deepen their knowledge through repeatedly acting and then reflecting on the action, can develop skills through practice, can construct new understandings of the world when placed in new situations, and can extend their learning as they bring their knowledge back to the formal classroom. In a nutshell, experiential learning can teach students the skills they need for real-world activities, it motivates students and creates self-directed learners who can tackle problems more easily. Particularly for science teaching it is important to train in scientific method and scientific attitude. Learning by experience also assists in the acquisition of skills and qualities while working in groups and to understand the manipulation of tools and equipment.

Intended Learning Objectives of the action are:

A basic understanding of the following environmental and social themes: climate change, greenhouse gasses, the consequences of climate change, adaptation pathways, renewable energy technologies, community energy initiatives, UN 'Sustainable Energy for All' global initiative for universal energy access.

A basic understanding of the following technical themes: the photovoltaic phenomenon, solar panel assembly, working with tools.

Outline of Training Activity

During the first 2-hour workshop on environmental and social issues caused by climate change the following topics are discussed: an introduction to climate change, the earth's energy balance, the greenhouse gasses and energy balance, the impacts on physical systems, the consequences of climate change & adaptation, the science consensus and the climate change debate, and mitigation strategies. During the second 2-hour workshop, renewable energy technologies are presented as a solution to climate change issues and energy equality and access. Wind and solar energy are explained with the presentation of wind turbines and solar modules. Large scale application of these technologies, such as solar parks and wind farms are presented and community energy initiatives around Europe are explained. Further on, the UN 'Sustainable Energy for All' global initiative for universal energy access, improvement of energy efficiency, and increase of the use of renewable energy, are explained, with a global perspective on energy equality. Examples of electrification case studies in rural Africa are presented from the SmartRue research group.

During the two 4-hour 'Engineering in Practice' workshops, the high school students have a unique opportunity to engage with a renewable energy technology, such as photovoltaic electricity, with a practical hands-on experience. Initially, they are exposed to information on the photovoltaic phenomenon and its application on solar modules, along with background information and off-grid and grid-tied renewable energy systems. Simple circuit diagrams are drawn up by the students in order to design the solar panel to be constructed for charging a 12V battery. This is a simple engineering task that provides

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

the students with an appreciation of the principles of engineering in practice. Once the amount of solar cells and the connection setup required are decided, the students have a chance to construct the module with simple tools and materials. Gender equality associated with manual work is addressed throughout the construction process making sure both male and female students participate equally. While the construction is carried out, all aspects of solar module manufacturing are discussed and explained, such as the thickness of the glass surface, the importance of keeping the construction clean and avoiding particles to reside on the solar cells, etc. This creates a conceptual link between the manual process that the students experience and the actual activities in an industrial solar module manufacturing facility. Once the construction is completed, the students perform electrical experiments on the module, testing it for open circuit voltage, short circuit current and calculating the power produced once connected to a 12V battery. The optimum inclination of the solar module is found experimentally and the importance of orientation and inclination of solar panels is discussed. The actual act of implementing a solar panel design that the students have made creates a direct association between engineering design and engineering products in use.

Evaluation approach

The training activity is evaluated through questionnaires provided to the students after they complete the action.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.2 Workshop Supporting a Glocal Energy Transition

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Plan

Supporting a glocal energy transition: from local energy communities to global simulation networks

Overview

Hosting partner: JRC

Co-organizing partners: RWTH Aachen University / Politecnico di Torino

Planned date: 9-10/11/2022

Type of Activity: Seminar

Contact: Antonio De Paola / antonio.de-paola@ec.europa.eu

Short Description

The event is a two-day seminar aimed at disseminating the research activities and fostering the community discourse on two key topics investigated by JRC Smart Grid Interoperability lab and its partners: Geographically-Distributed RTDS and Renewable Energy Communities. The event will see the participation of distinguished speakers from academia, industry and public institutions, which will discuss the topics of RECs and GD-RTDS in the wider context of the energy transition. A GD-RTDS experiment will be conducted in collaboration with RWTH Aachen University and Politecnico di Torino during the event, in order to demonstrate the important role that GD-RTDS can play in assessing new technologies and solutions for the energy transition at a local level.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

GD-RTDS is a research topic that is very well aligned with the focus of the EG-2 project on validation of cyber-physical systems and on tools and services for lab interfacing and data exchange. The objective of the seminar is to present the topic of GD-RTDS to the wider power system community, framing it in the larger context of the energy transition and practically demonstrating its application and potential impact at the local level. The seminar will also discuss the theme of Renewable Energy Communities, which is strictly related to the general focus of Erigrad on smart grids and smart energy systems and contributes to provide a wider and more comprehensive overview of the research efforts conducted by JRC and its partners on the timely challenge of the energy transition.

Target group(s)

The event is targeted to the general power system community, with a particular focus on researchers and industrial practitioners.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.3 Panel Session at IEEE PES General Meeting 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan

16-05-2023

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Panel Session at IEEE PES GM

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): 18/Jul/2022

Type of Activity: Special Sessions and Panel Sessions

Contact: Zhiwang Feng and Mazher Syed, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

This panel session titled “Cloud-Based Control and Co-Simulation of Multi-Party Resources in Energy Internet” will be organized by Dr. Mazher Syed (UoS) at the IEEE Power and Energy Society General Meeting 2022, in Denver, United States.

The intended audiences include (but not limited to) academic researchers and industrial engineers working on the development and validation of decentralized and distributed control of DERs in power systems within the frame of energy internet.

The panel session is relevant to the activities of JRA 2.1 and JRA 2.2 where testbeds and platforms for the validation of power and energy system control algorithms are under development.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

Information and communication technology continues to shift the modern power system into the “Energy Internet” paradigm. Various multi-party resources are controlled by edge-cloud computational resources with information exchange among them via communication system. The architectures, functions, algorithms, and validation tools towards this future vision need to be further investigated. This panel session comprises presentations from academics from US, Europe and Asia, disseminating state-of-the-art algorithms for control of distributed energy resources and tools/platforms for their validation with confidence.

The developments of Task JRA2.2 relating to geographically distributed simulations will be disseminated at the panel, highlighting their capability and application within the paradigm of Energy Internet.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

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- To inform of the state-of-the-art developments in distributed controls for power systems.
- To demonstrate the new testbeds and platforms under development that can support the validation of novel control schemes within the energy internet paradigm with confidence.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

An audience that has attended this panel session will be able to:

- Beginners: Describe, discuss and relate to distributed control in power systems: their functionality, applicability, and suitability for adoption in power systems.
- Intermediate: Identify scenarios where the presented control approaches can be employed and/or where the presented testbeds can be employed for testing controls.
- Expert: Employ testbed for validation of controls.
- Expert: Criticize and propose advances to techniques through further research.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

This panel session will be carried out at the IEEE PES GM 2022 conference and will include the following presentations:

- Dr Mazher Syed, University of Strathclyde, "Co-simulation techniques for geographically distributed research infrastructures"
- Dr Tung-Lam Nguyen, Florida International University, "Distributed control and optimization in power systems"
- Dr Ha Nguyen, University of Connecticut, "Real-time hybrid co-simulation for large-scale power system using RTDS and TSAT"
- Prof Xu Yan, Nanyang Technological University, "Data-driven coordinated control of networked-microgrid systems"

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organisers (NA3-TrainingActivity-Feedback-Form)

No formal evaluation of the panel session is feasible at such conferences, however, a qualitative assessment through audience participation and engagement can be undertaken.

A.2.4 Nuffield Research Placement at Strathclyde

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ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Nuffield Research Placements in Sustainable Aviation at Strathclyde

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)

Co-organizing partners: N/A

Planned date (approximate): August 2022

Type of Activity: Training of High School Students

Contact: Zhiwang Feng and Mazher Syed, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

Three internships for high-school students to work on projects related to Sustainable Aviation will be offered at the dynamic Power Systems Laboratory in collaboration with Nuffield research Placements.

The intended audience is high school students in Year 12, working on their applications to universities for their undergraduate.

This internship will allow the students to appreciate the experimental methods currently under development at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (DPSL) for the characterization of arc faults within aero-electrical power systems. These experimental methods support the overarching agenda of Erigrd 2.0 in accelerating the validation and deployment of novel technologies.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

The decarbonisation of aviation towards net-zero emissions flight is an important step towards Governments' ambition to realize a net-zero future. Immediate action towards the electrification and hydrogenation of aircraft is necessary to support ambition. While research is carried out at the University of Strathclyde supporting various aspects of the ambition, at the same time it is necessary to educate and motivate pupils about the exciting challenges we address on a daily basis. To encourage the students to uptake STEM courses for their further education.

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

This module intends to ...

- To introduce the pupils to sustainable aviation and the concept of electrification of aircraft.
- To introduce the challenges brought forward by electrification of aircraft.

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- To inform of the state-of-the-art research experimental research undertaken at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory to address the challenges that arise from DC series arcs.
- To demonstrate dc series arc phenomena through experimental rig at DPSL.
- To introduce the pupils to research by undertaking literature review on the focused subject
- To analyze datasets and samples obtained through the experiments to appreciate the damage to the surroundings due to an arc event.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

- Describe, discuss and relate to efforts towards decarbonisation of aviation.
- Describe and discuss the challenges with electrification of aircraft.
- Undertake elementary critical review on selected topics of focus.
- Analyse and group datasets.

A.2.5 Tutorial at IEEE SMC 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Validating Smart Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society (SMC)

Planned date: 09.10.2022

Type of Activity: Tutorial (at IEEE SMC 2022 conference)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply in Europe is the integration of distributed, renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities and network operators are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technological developments, partly controllable loads (energy storage systems, heat pumps, electric vehicle supply equipment, etc.), integration with other energy sources (i.e., hybrid grids), changing regulatory rules, and the market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Sophisticated design approaches together with proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a so-called smart grid. Nowadays, the digitalization of smart grids and smart energy systems (electricity, gas, heat, etc.) plays a dominant role and provides the basis for future innovations.

During the last two decades a growing number of various research, technology development, and innovation activities have already been carried out in this domain. A various number of demonstration projects have already shown the applicability of the proposed smart grid approaches. Also, the extension of the smart grid concept which focuses on electric energy to multi-domain energy – towards smart energy systems – has been carried out during the last years.

While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviours, it is expected that the system-level testing will need to play a significantly larger role in the development and roll-out of future solutions and technologies. Validation approaches, concepts, and corresponding tools for smart grids and smart energy systems are still not mature enough for effective usage. A key element in this context is the human factor as well as educated professionals, engineers, and researchers understanding the needs and methods for complex smart grids and smart energy systems validation in a multi-domain and cyber-physical manner. This is partly lacking today.

In summarizing, the following research and development topics are not sufficiently covered:

- Domain-specific adaptations of previously developed abstract validation procedures and corresponding concepts, methods, and tools are required to address advanced applications (low-inertia grids, microgrids, hybrid grids, etc.),
- Common and well-understood reference scenarios, use cases, and test case profiles for smart energy

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

systems need to be provided to power and energy systems engineers and researchers; also, proper validation benchmark criteria and key performance indicators, as well as interoperability measures for validating smart grids and smart energy systems, need to be developed, extended, and shared with engineers and researchers in Europe,

- Harmonization and standardization of multi-domain cyber-physical systems-based evaluation and testing procedures are necessary, and
- Well-educated professionals, engineers, and researchers understanding smart grid and smart energy systems configurations in a multi-domain and cyber-physical manner addressing the upcoming energy transition need to be educated and trained on a broad scale.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing validation methods and tools for validating smart energy systems which are currently being developed in ERIGrid 2.0.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

A driving force for the realization of a sustainable energy supply is the integration of renewable energy resources. Due to their stochastic generation behaviour, energy utilities are confronted with a more complex operation of the underlying power grids. Additionally, due to technological developments, controllable loads, integration with other energy sources, changing regulatory rules, and market liberalization, the system's operation needs adaptation. Proper operational concepts and intelligent automation provide the basis to turn the existing power system into an intelligent entity, a smart grid. While reaping the benefits that come along with those intelligent behaviours, it is expected that system-level developments and testing will play a significantly larger role in realizing future solutions and technologies. Proper validation approaches, concepts, and tools are partly missing until now.

This tutorial aims to tackle the above-mentioned requirements by introducing validation methods and tools for validating smart energy systems which are currently being developed in ERIGrid 2.0.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems in the form of scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

Outline of Training Activity

The tutorial covers the following topics:

- Introduction to smart energy systems
- The ERIGrid 2.0 vision and approach
- Validation and testing approaches
- Selected validation examples

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.6 Panel Session at IEEE ISGT Europe 2022

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ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan Panel Session at IEEE ISGT Europe

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)

Co-organizing partners: ICCS-NTUA

Planned date (approximate): 10/Oct/2022 – 12/Oct/2022

Type of Activity: Special Sessions and Panel Sessions

Contact: Zhiwang Feng and Mazher Syed, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Short Description

A description of the selection of topics, the hosting partners, intended audience and why the course is relevant to ERIGrid 2.0

This panel session named “Pushing the Boundaries of Real-Time Simulation for Validation of Future Complex Power System” will be organized by Dr. Mazher Syed (UoS) and Dr. Thomas Strasser (Austrian Institute of Technology, Austria) at the IEEE Power and Energy Society’s (PES) Innovative Smart Grid Technologies (ISGT) Europe Conference, to be held at Novi Sad, Serbia in October 2022.

The intended audiences include (but not limited to) academic researchers and industrial engineers working on the power system real-time simulations, controller and power hardware-in-the-loop methods for validation of complex power systems and geographically distributed simulations.

This panel session will disseminate research breakthroughs to the intended audiences with various backgrounds, including the developments within task JRA 2.2 of the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

Why is this training activity required? What specific outcomes of EG-2 are conveyed here?

Link to appropriate studies, directives, project ambition, etc.

This panel session focuses on the novel real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems, disseminating the advancements that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of future grid solutions. This is essential to provide both the academic researcher and industrial practitioners who are interested in the hardware-in-the-loop simulation and geographically distributed real-time simulation with the most recent research advancements and stimulate new pathways for further research and development. The reported developments will be key enabler for more robust power hardware-in-the-loop simulation setups with high fidelity over extended operating constraints.

This activity directly links to the developments within JRA 2.2. Developments and advancements achieved within the project will be disseminated.

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Training Objectives and Intended Learning Objectives (ILOs)

As Training Objectives Describe the competences that should be conveyed to the learners in your technical perspective.

- To inform of the state-of-the-art developments and breakthroughs in real-time simulations to support validation of complex power and energy systems.
- Demonstrate applications of techniques with real-world examples.

In addition, try to specify the expected learning outcome as “Intended Learning Objectives” – specific measurable abilities that the course is intended to convey. We will use Bloom’s revised taxonomy to describe the school’s objective – Appendix 1 has an illustration to reference

An audience that has attended this panel session will be able to:

- Beginners: Describe, discuss and relate to real-time simulation techniques: their functionality, applicability, and suitability for validation of complex power and energy systems.
- Intermediate: Identify scenarios where the presented techniques can be employed.
- Expert: Employ techniques for validation of complex power and energy systems.
- Expert: Criticize and propose advances to techniques through further research.

Outline of Training Activity

Describe here the key components and learning activities comprising the training activity. A time schedule can be included here if available.

This panel session will be carried out at the IEEE PES ISGT-Europe 2022 conference and will include the following presentations:

- “Shaping Future Power Systems with Real-Time Simulation” contributed by Ms. Kati Sidwall (RTDS technologies, Canada)
- Interface Algorithm for Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation: Addressing the Stability and Accuracy Constraints” contributed by Dr. Alexandros Paspatis (National Technical University of Athens, Greece)
- “Ultra High-Fidelity Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation for Microgrids and Electrical Distribution Networks” contributed by Dr. Adrien Genic (Typhoon HIL, Serbia)
- “Experiences with Next Generation Validation Methods for the Derisking of the Renewables Dominated Grids: Black Start” contributed by Mr. Zhiwang Feng (University of Strathclyde)

Evaluation approach

How is the success of the training activity evaluated? Note EG-2 requests an evaluation only by the organisers (NA3-TrainingActivity-Feedback-Form)

No formal evaluation of the panel session is feasible at such conferences, however, a qualitative assessment through audience participation and engagement can be undertaken.

A.2.7 European Researchers Night 2020

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan European Researcher's Night 2020 (ERN 2020) Participation

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT
 Co-organizing partners: ERN 2020 organizers of Vienna event
 Planned date: 27.11.2020

Type of Activity: Training to the General Public (ERN) – online presentation

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services provided by the coordinator AIT to the general public.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information to the public in the form of an online presentation.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show the higher complexity of future energy systems and introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of it in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

Outline of Training Activity

The activity consists of a brief overview presentation.

Evaluation approach

An evaluation of the contributions to the ERN 2020 is planned by the organization team in the form of an online questionnaire.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.2.8 European Researchers Night 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Plan European Researcher's Night 2022 (ERN 2022) Participation

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: ERN 2022 organizers of Vienna event

Planned date: 30.09.2022

Type of Activity: Booth/exhibition

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Elisabeth Mrakotsky, elisabeht.mrakotsky@ait.ac.at

Short Description

Introduction and overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 validation, testing, and education services provided by the coordinator AIT to the general public.

Motivation / Rationale / Training Need

The training is required to provide general information to the public through a booth at the ERN 2022.

Target group(s)

All ERIGrid 2.0 stakeholders (academia/research, industry, energy utilities, standardization, general public).

Training Objectives and Intended Learning Outcomes (ILOs)

This module intends to show future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduces the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

Outline of Training Activity

This activity consists of a booth with monitors and simulation-based scenario tools.

Evaluation approach

An evaluation of the contributions to the ERN 2020 is planned by the organization team.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3 Activity Reports

A.3.1 Environmental Education through the Construction of a PV Module

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Environmental Education and Renewable Energy Technologies for High Schools

Overview

Hosting partner: 1st Arsakeio Tositsio General High School of Ekali

Co-organizing partners: SmartRUE, School of the Earth

Delivered date: 30th of March, 7th of April, 11th of April

Type of Activity: Training of High School Students

Contact: Kostas Latoufis, latoufis@power.ece.ntua.gr

Agenda and Schedule of the event

30th of March: Workshop on environmental and social issues caused by climate change and renewable energy technologies

7th of April: Practical workshop for the construction of a solar panel (part 1)

11th of April: Practical workshop for the construction of a solar panel (part 2)

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

20 high school students

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

During the first 2-hour workshop on environmental and social issues caused by climate change the following topics are discussed: an introduction to climate change, the earth's energy balance, the greenhouse gasses and energy balance, the impacts on physical systems, the consequences of climate change & adaptation, the science consensus and the climate change debate, and mitigation strategies. During the second 2-hour workshop, renewable energy technologies are presented as a solution to climate change issues and energy equality and access. Wind and solar energy are explained with the presentation of wind turbines and solar modules. Large scale application of these technologies, such as solar parks and wind farms are presented and community energy initiatives around Europe are explained. Further on, the UN 'Sustainable Energy for All' global initiative for universal energy access, improvement of energy efficiency, and increase of the use of renewable energy, are explained, with a global perspective on energy equality. Examples of electrification case studies in rural Africa are presented from the SmartRue research group.

During the two 4-hour 'Engineering in Practice' workshops, the high school students have a unique opportunity to engage with a renewable energy technology, such as photovoltaic electricity, with a practical hands-on experience. Initially, they are exposed to information on the photovoltaic phenomenon and its application on solar modules, along with background information and off-grid and grid-tied renewable energy systems. Simple circuit diagrams are drawn up by the students in order to design the solar panel to be constructed for charging a 12V battery. This is a simple engineering task that provides the students with an appreciation of the principles of engineering in

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practice. Once the amount of solar cells and the connection setup required are decided, the students have a chance to construct the module with simple tools and materials. Gender equality associated with manual work is addressed throughout the construction process making sure both male and female students participate equally. While the construction is carried out, all aspects of solar module manufacturing are discussed and explained, such as the thickness of the glass surface, the importance of keeping the construction clean and avoiding particles to reside on the solar cells, etc. This creates a conceptual link between the manual process that the students experience and the actual activities in an industrial solar module manufacturing facility. Once the construction is completed, the students perform electrical experiments on the module, testing it for open circuit voltage, short circuit current and calculating the power produced once connected to a 12V battery. The optimum inclination of the solar module is found experimentally and the importance of orientation and inclination of solar panels is discussed. The actual act of implementing a solar panel design that the students have made creates a direct association between engineering design and engineering products in use.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Aspects of experiential learning were developed, as a way of learning that supports students in applying their knowledge and conceptual understanding to real-world problems. The students were given the opportunity to learn in a real-life practical situation by constructing a solar panel, thus the learning experience become significantly more powerful. Students deepened their knowledge through repeatedly acting and then reflecting on the action, developed skills through practice. Particularly for science teaching it was an important training in the scientific method and scientific attitude. Finally, skills and qualities were acquired while working in groups and while manipulating tools and equipment.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

15 high school students participated.

A.3.2 Workshop Supporting Glocal Energy Transition

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Supporting a glocal energy transition: from local energy communities to global simulation networks

Overview

Hosting partner: Joint Research Centre (JRC)

Co-organizing partners: RWTH Aachen, Politecnico di Torino, Ensiel consortium

Delivered date: 9-10/11/2022

Type of Activity: *Workshop*

Contact: Antonio De Paola (antonio.de-paola@ec.europa.eu)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Day 1 – Renewable Energy Communities for a local energy transition

13:30 - 13:50 **Welcome**

- Gianluca Fulli (European Commission - JRC)
- Konstantinos Stamatis (European Commission – DG ENER)

13:50 - 15:10 **Objectives and challenges of regulation on Energy Communities**

- Four talks (20 minutes each)
- Valerie Reif (Florence School of Regulation)
 - Marco Merlo (Politecnico di Milano)
 - Ludwig Karg (BAUM Consult)
 - Vincenzo Trovato (Università di Trento)

15:10 - 15:20 **Coffee break**

15:20 - 16:40 **Energy Communities: success stories, technological and social developments**

- Four talks (20 minutes each)
- Sergio Olivero (Politecnico di Torino)
 - Dimitrios Thomas (European Commission - JRC) – “Added value of sharing storage in energy communities”
 - Alexandros Chronis (National Technical University of Athens)
 - Daniele Paci (European Commission – JRC)

16:40 - 17:20 **Round Table**

- Topic: *The role of energy communities in the future decarbonized power system*
- Moderator: Antonio De Paola (European Commission - JRC)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Participants: Ludwig Karg (BAUM Consult), Valerie Reif (Florence School of Regulation), Konstantinos Stamatidis (European Comm. - DG ENER), Sergio Olivero (Politecnico di Torino), Alberto Prospero (ENERBIT)

17:20 – 17:30 **Conclusions**
 19:00 – 21:00 **Social Dinner**

Day 2 – Internet-of-labs supporting the energy transition

- 09:00 - 09:20 **Welcome**
 - Evangelos Kotsakis (European Commission - JRC)
 - Domenico Villacci (ENSIEL Director, Università di Napoli Federico II)
- 09:20 - 09:40 **Internet-of-labs: an innovative vision to support the energy transition**
 Ettore Bompard (ENET RT-Lab Politecnico di Torino)
- 09:40 - 10:00 **Multi-site co-simulation**
 Antonello Monti (RWTH Aachen)
- 10:00 – 10:20 **The ERIGRID 2.0 project**
 Thomas Strasser (Austrian Institute of Technology)
- 10:20 - 10:30 **Coffee break**
- 10:30 - 10:45 **Energy communities as an effective tool for the future energy system: the demo experiment**
 JRC + RWTH Aachen + ENET RT-Lab (intro + description of laboratories)
- 10:45 – 11:00 **Live experiment of Geographically-Distributed Real-Time Simulations**
 Demonstration of the support of energy communities to power system operation
- 11:00 – 11:45 **Roundtable**
 Topic: What comes next? Bottlenecks and opportunities for the internet of labs
 Moderator: Marcelo Masera (EST@energycenter, Politecnico di Torino)
 Participants: Andrea Benigni (FZI) + Cyprian Peters (RTDS Technologies) + Ravinder Venugopal (OPAL-RT) + Sébastien Lepy (CRESYM)
- 11:45 – 12:00 **Conclusions**
 Marcelo Masera (EST@energycenter, Politecnico di Torino)
- 12:00 – 13:00 **Lunch** (JRC - Piccola mensa)

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

- Ali Sadaqat (University of Lorraine)
- Alic Sadjja (Università di Trento)
- Benedetto Giorgio (Politecnico di Torino)
- Benigni Andrea (FZ-Juelich)
- Bompard Ettore (Politecnico di Torino)
- Bonfiglio Andrea (Università di Genova)
- Bruno Sergio (Politecnico di Bari)
- Brustio Mariano (European Commission - JRC)
- Cavaliere Diego (RSE)
- Checola Silvia (MBS Consulting)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

- Chiumeo Riccardo (RSE)
- Chronis Alexandros (NTUA)
- Clerici Alessio (RSE)
- De Caro Fabrizio (Università del Sannio)
- De Paola Antonio (European Commission - JRC)
- Dejuanvela Pablo (Università di Trento)
- Donnari Elena (European Commission - JRC)
- Fulli Gianluca (European Commission - JRC)
- Gandolfi Chiara (RSE)
- Garbellini Paolo
- Giannoccaro Giovanni (Politecnico di Bari)
- Karg Ludwig (BAUM Group)
- Kotsakis Evangelos (European Commission - JRC)
- Lepy Sebastien (CRESYM)
- Maserà Marcelo (Politecnico di Torino)
- Mazza Andrea (Politecnico di Torino)
- Merlo Marco (Politecnico di Milano)
- Monti Antonello (RWTH Aachen)
- Olivero Sergio (Politecnico di Torino)
- Paci Daniele (European Commission - JRC)
- Peters Cyprian (RTDS)
- Pinto Luisia
- Prospero Alberto (Enerbit)
- Raggini Diego (RSE)
- Rancilio Giuliano (Politecnico di Milano)
- Reif Valerie (Florence School of Regulation)
- Roesgen Eric (European Commission - JRC)
- Rossi Mansueto (Università di Genova)
- Sacchi Paolo
- Stamatīs Konstantinos (European Commission – DG-ENER)
- Strasser Thomas (AIT)
- Thomas Dimitrios (European Commission - JRC)
- Trovato Vincenzo (Università di Trento)
- Venugopal Ravinder (OPAL-RT)
- Veroni Alessandro (RSE)
- Vogel Steffen (RWTH Aachen)
- Zanoni Michele (RSE)

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

The workshop, organized in collaboration with Politecnico di Torino, RWTH Aachen and the Ensiel consortium, has disseminated the research activities of the JRC Smart Grid Interoperability Laboratory, fostering the community discourse on the topics of renewable energy communities and

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

global simulation networks. The event has seen the participation of distinguished international speakers from academia, industry and public institutions, which have discussed these subjects in the wider context of the energy transition. The first day of the event has focused on energy communities, presenting some of the latest success stories in the field and discussing their role in the future decarbonized power system under a rapidly changing regulatory framework. The list of speakers included Sergio Olivero (Comunità Energetica di Magliano Alpi) who presented the results of the lab access activity conducted by his institution in the Smart Grid Interoperability Laboratory (JRC Ispra) in the context of the TA2 Erigrd work package. The second day of the seminar focused on the internet-of-labs paradigm, discussing its impact in supporting the energy transition and showcasing a real-time demonstrative experiment with the joint participation of six European laboratories. The discussions and the experiment are strictly linked with the Erigrd work package JRA2.

Achievements and learning outcomes

The participants familiarised on two main topics:

Day 1: Renewable Energy Communities, with a particular focus on regulatory objectives and challenges, technological and social developments, and the role of energy communities in driving the energy transition

Day2: Internet-of-labs: a live multi-site laboratory experiment showcased the capabilities of Geographically-Distributed Real-Time Simulations and demonstrated their potential role in supporting the design and operation of decarbonized energy systems

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The hybrid workshop was attended in total by 47 persons (30 in person and 17 remotely). Out of 47 participants, 37 were project external persons.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.3 Panel Session at IEEE PES General Meeting 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report

Panel Session: Coordinated Control and Co-Simulation of Power Systems in Energy Internet

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)

Co-organizing partners: NA

Delivered date: 18/Jul/2022

Type of Activity: [Special Sessions and Panel Sessions](#)

Contact: Zhiwang Feng, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Time	Seesion	Name	Affiliation	Presentation Title
15.00-15.05	Welcoming	Prof. Graeme Burt	UoS	---
15.05-15.25	Presentation 1	Dr. Mazher Syed	UoS	Complex Power and Energy Systems Validation through interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories
15.25-15.45	Presentation 2	Dr. Tung-Lam Nguyen	Florida International University	Distributed Control and Optimization in Power Systems
15.45-16.05	Presentation 3	Dr. Ha Thi Nguyen	University of Connecticut	Real-Time Hybrid Co-Simulation for Large-Scale Power System using RTDS and TSAT
16.05 -16.25	Presentation 4	Dr. Xu Yan	Nanyang Technological University	Data-Driven Coordinated Control of Networked-Microgrid Systems
16.25 -16.35	Presentation 5	Prof. Graeme Burt	UoS	Introduction to TF: Cloud-Based Control and Co-Simulation of Multi-party Resources in Energy Internet
16.35-17.00	Q&A	---	---	---

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

NA

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This panel session, organized by UoS, comprised 5 main invited presentations covering the following topics: (i) Complex Power and Energy Systems Validation through interconnection of Geographically Distributed Research Laboratories, (ii) Distributed Control and Optimization in Power Systems, (iii) Real-Time Hybrid Co-Simulation for Large-Scale Power System using RTDS and TSAT, (iv) Data-Driven Coordinated Control of Networked-Microgrid Systems, (v) Introduction to TF: Cloud-Based Control and Co-Simulation of Multi-party Resources in Energy Internet. All presentations in this panel session were dedicated to showcasing the application of the novel real-time simulation and geographically distributed co-simulation techniques to the validation of complex power systems and the cloud-based coordinated control in energy internet. The objective of these presentations also involves disseminating the advancements that enable the real-time co-simulation validation methodology being applied to the validation of novel coordinated control in modern power systems. The reported developments are the key enabler for applying the novel coordinated control to complex power systems through cloud-based co-simulation techniques. These are essential to offer both academic researchers and industrial practitioners who are interested in the geographically distributed real-time simulation and cloud-based

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

power system coordinated control with the most recent research advancements and stimulate pathways for further research and development. Through this panel session, the breakthroughs, developments, and advancements achieved within the JRA 2.1 and JRA 2.2 of the ERIGrid 2.0 project have been disseminated to the intended audiences.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This panel session provided a forum for academic researchers and industrial practitioners to exchange knowledge and share research experiences on innovative real-time co-simulation techniques aimed at validating coordinated control techniques for complex power systems. The research advancements on the emerging geographically distributed real-time co-simulation techniques that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of the cloud-aided coordinated control schemes have been disseminated to the intended audiences who are interested in real-time simulation and expertise in the power system design and control. Moreover, through disseminating the breakthroughs, developments, and advancements achieved within the JRA 2.1 and JRA2.2 of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, the participants acquired a more in-depth understanding of the ongoing research activities of the ERIGrid project and familiarised themselves with the scopes of ERIGrid project. This, in turn, stimulated new collaborative research activities using the ERIGrid 2.0 Transnational Access program between UoS and other research institutes.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The amount of participants in this panel session is 30, out of which 28 participants were project external persons.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

NA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.4 Nuffield Research Placement at Strathclyde

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Nuffield Research Placement at Strathclyde-Supporting Sustainable Aviation

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)

Co-organizing partners: NA

Delivered date: August 2022

Type of Activity: Training of High School Students

Contact: Zhiwang Feng, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Agenda and Schedule of the event

First Placement: 25th July 2022 to 5th August 2022

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Student 1: Callum Ford

Student 2: Lewis McGuire

Student 3: Constance Fogarty

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

The decarbonisation of aviation towards net-zero emissions flight is an important step towards Governments' ambition to realize a net-zero future. Immediate action toward the electrification and hydrogenation of aircraft is necessary to support ambition. While research is carried out at the University of Strathclyde supporting various aspects of the ambition, at the same time it is necessary to educate and motivate pupils about the exciting challenges we address on a daily basis. Three internships for high school students in Year 12 to work on projects related to Sustainable Aviation were offered at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory at UoS in collaboration with Nuffield Research Placements.

During the two-week internship, these students were able to appreciate the experimental methods currently under development at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory for the characterization of arc faults within aero-electrical power systems. These experimental methods support the overarching agenda of Erigrd 2.0 in accelerating the validation and deployment of novel technologies. Firstly, the concept of sustainable aviation and the research and development of electrification of aircraft and its associated challenges were introduced to the pupils. Furthermore, accompanied by the physical lab demonstration of the DC series arc phenomena through an experimental rig, the pupils were informed of the state-of-the-art research experimental research

1

undertaken at the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory to address the challenges that arise from DC series arcs. In addition, to facilitate the pupils with preliminary research skills, elementary critical literature reviews on the more electric aircraft aided sustainable aviation and DC series arc characterization have been undertaken by the pupils. At the final stage of the internship, the pupils carried out the hands-on experimental analysis of the datasets and samples obtained through the experiments to appreciate the damage to the surroundings due to an arc event.

Achievements and learning outcomes

During this internship, the concept of Sustainable Aviation along with the research and development of aircraft electrification has been demonstrated to high-school students. Through this experience, we were able to expand their knowledge base and broaden their horizons, as well as ignite their interest and motivation for further exploration of this research area. In addition, the pupils were given the opportunity to get involved in real-world DC arc experiments, which enabled them to develop their perspectives and skills in experimental validation and data analysis. These acquired skills enable the pupils to apply their prior knowledge and conceptual understanding into practice. Furthermore, the knowledge and skills acquired by the pupils during this internship not only support the student's academic pursuits, but also better prepare them for their undergraduate studies.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

3 high school students participated.

2

A.3.5 Tutorial at IEEE SMC 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Validating Smart Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics Society (SMC)

Delivered date: 09.10.2022

Type of Activity: Tutorial (at IEEE SMC 2022 conference)

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The tutorial covered the following topics:

- Introduction to smart energy systems
- The ERIGrid 2.0 vision and approach
- Validation and testing approaches
- Selected validation examples

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

Around 5 participants joined the hybrid event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This tutorial discussed and summarized the main needs and requirements as well as the status quo in research and development related to the engineering and validation of cyber-physical energy systems. Also, validation examples and short demos have been presented. Finally, research trends and necessary future activities have been outlined as well.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This module showed the expected future energy systems' higher complexity in scenarios with different penetration levels of renewables. It also introduced the necessity of system-level design and validation approaches based on simulations and laboratory testing as well as the combination of them in a hardware-in-the-loop manner.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The following information about the tutorial was made available by SMC:

- No. of registered persons: n/a
- No. of attendees: 5
- No. of project external persons: 5

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

No evaluation has been carried out.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.6 Panel Session ISGT EU 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report Panel Session: Pushing the Boundaries of Real-Time Simulations for Validation of Future Complex Power Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: University of Strathclyde (UoS)

Co-organizing partners: National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) & Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)

Delivered date: 11/Oct/2022

Type of Activity: [Special Sessions and Panel Sessions](#)

Contact: Zhiwang Feng, zhiwang.feng@strath.ac.uk

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Time	Seession	Name	Affiliation	Presentation Title
14.00-14.05	Welcoming	Dr. Mazher Syed	UoS	---
14.05-14.25	Presentation 1	Ms. Kati Sidwall	RTDS Technology	Shaping Future Power System with Real-Time Simulation
14.25-14.45	Presentation 2	Dr. Alexandros Paspatis	NTUA	Interface Algorithms for Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation: Addressing the Stability and Accuracy Constraints
14.45-15.05	Presentation 3	Dr. Adrirn Genic	Typhoon HIL	Ultra High-Fidelity Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulations for Microgrids and Electrical Distribution Networks
15.05 -15.25	Presentation 4	Mr. Zhiwang Feng	UoS	Experiences with Next Generation Validation Methods for the Derisking of the Renewable Dominated Grids: Black-Start
15.25 -15.40	Q&A	---	---	---

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

This panel session, organized by UoS in collaboration with NTUA and AIT, comprised 4 main invited presentations covering the following topics: (i) Shaping Future Power System with Real-Time Simulation, (ii) Interface Algorithms for Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation: Addressing the Stability and Accuracy Constraints, (iii) Ultra High-Fidelity Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulations for Microgrids and Electrical Distribution Networks, (iv) Experiences with Next Generation Validation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Methods for the Derisking of the Renewable Dominated Grids: Black-Start. All of these presentations focused on the novel real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems, disseminating the advancements that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of future grid solutions. The reported developments are the key enabler for more robust power hardware-in-the-loop simulation setups with high fidelity over extended operating constraints. These are essential to provide both academic researchers and industrial practitioners who are interested in the hardware-in-the-loop simulation and geographically distributed real-time simulation with the most recent research advancements, stimulating new pathways for further research and collaborations. Through this panel session, the breakthroughs and the developments and advancements achieved within the JRA 2.2 of the ERIGRID 2.0 project have been disseminated to the intended audiences.

Achievements and learning outcomes

This panel session facilitated a knowledge-sharing and research-experience exchange environment among the ERIGRID partners on innovative real-time simulation techniques for the validation of complex power systems. The advancements that are pushing beyond existing limitations of the real-time validation methodology toward high-fidelity, trusted validation of future grid solutions have been disseminated to the intended audiences who are interested in the hardware-in-the-loop simulation and geographically distributed real-time simulation. In addition, through disseminating the breakthroughs and the developments and advancements achieved within the JRA 2.2 of the ERIGRID 2.0 project, the participants including academic researchers and industrial practitioners acquired a more in-depth understanding of the ongoing research activities of the ERIGRID project and familiarised themselves with the scopes of ERIGRID project.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The amount of participants in this panel session is 28, out of which 25 participants were project external persons.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.7 European Researcher Night 2020

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report European Researcher's Night 2020 (ERN 2020) Participation

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: ERN 2020 organizers of Vienna event

Delivered date: 27.11.2020

Type of Activity: Training to the General Public (ERN) – online presentation

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The ERN 2020 in Vienna was organised as an online event with different presentation channels. The ERIGrid 2.0-related presentation was given in Channel #1; the related agenda was:

- 01:13 Die mysteriösen Phänomene der Quantenphysik
- 21:00 Coronavirus – ist der Erreger schon mutiert?
- 41:19 Die Welt der Mikroorganismen – was ihr schon immer wissen wolltet
- 1:01:06 Dunkle Materie und wie wir sie finden
- 1:22:19 Gesundheit – überschätzen wir unseren Körper?
- 1:40:14 Verschwörungstheorien – gibt es sie schon seit Jahrtausenden?
- 2:00:27 Was macht eigentlich die Teilchenphysik?
- 2:22:01 Visualisierung der österreichischen Medienlandschaft durch digitale Methoden
- 2:43:23 Bestiarium Mesopotamicum
- 3:04:23 Introduction to Heritage Science Austria and Heritage Science projects at KHM
- 3:22:49 Centre of Image and Material Analysis in Cultural Heritage (CIMA)
- 3:44:17 Das Institut für Naturwissenschaften und Technologie in der Kunst (INTK)
- 4:05:31 Wien und die Wiener Gewässer – eine historische Spurensuche
- 4:25:02 Wood: IR-light. Tells you if you guessed the age right
- 4:44:57 LArchiv Archiv Österreichischer Landschaftsarchitektur, BOKU Wien
- 5:01:42 Microscopy and Heritage Science at the Angewandte
- 5:23:40 Seno-Therapien gegen Zellalterung
- 5:45:35 PatientInnen Involvierung in der Lungengefäßforschung
- **6:04:25 Smart Grids – Entwicklung und Validierung der Energiesysteme der Zukunft**
- 6:27:10 Bakterienkulturen: Was ist Natur, was ist Kultur?
- 6:38:03 Gastroenterology and Hepatology
- 6:54:43 Video Beiträge (FH Campus, Otele eGen und FH Technikum Wien)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

A couple of 100 participants joined the online event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Scientific activities and results from various domains/areas have been presented to the general public during the ERN 2020 online event. The agenda/schedule part of this report provides an overview of topics.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Information and outcomes/results of various scientific and technical achievements have been shared to the general public.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The event was attended by more than 7,500 visitors. The breakdown by channel looks like this:

- Presentation channel 1: 1950 visitors. Generally, there were always between 40 and 80 viewers online at the same time.
- Lecture channel 2: 1350 visitors. Generally, between 30 and 50 viewers were always online at the same time.
- Participation channel: 700 visitors. Generally, between 25 and 50 viewers were always online at the same time.
- Stage program channel and round table "Art and Research": 2200 visitors. In general, between 190 and 400 viewers were always online at the same time.
- Salzburg Kanal: 156 visitors
- Children's University TV: 700 visitors
- Youth Science Flash: 152 visitors
- Science Cafe: 300 visitors
- Radarchips on autonomous driving: 10 visitors

More than 170 scientists participated in the program, which was streamed through 6 channels and 2 Interactive Workshops. The program included a total of 46 lectures, 28 workshops, 24 video contributions, 6 science slams, 2 concerts, a science show, a round table and the Citizen Science Cafe.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

An online questionnaire was distributed by the ERN 2020 organisers, but the results have not been shared; therefore, no feedback information is available.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.8 European Researcher Night 2022

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report European Researcher’s Night 2022 (ERN 2022) Participation

Overview

Hosting partner: AIT

Co-organizing partners: ERN 2022 organizers of Vienna event

Delivered date: 30.09.2022

Type of Activity: Training to the General Public (ERN) – booth/exhibition

Contact: Thomas Strasser, thomas.strasser@ait.ac.at; Elisabeth Mrakotsky, elisabeht.mrakotsky@ait.ac.at

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The following figure provides a high-level overview of the agenda of the ERN 2022 in Vienna:

Interaktive wissenschaftliche Stationen	Spannende Workshops und Live-Vorträge	Ein buntes Kinderprogramm mit vielen Highlights
Das Science Slam Österreich-finale	Die Physik-Show mit Werner Gruber	Zahlreiche Experimente live vor Ort

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

A couple of 1,000 participants joined the online event; due to GDPR regulations, the attendance list cannot be shared.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

Scientific activities and results from various domains/areas have been presented to the general public during the ERN 2022 event.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Information and outcomes/results of various scientific and technical achievements have been shared with the general public.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

The following figures provide an overview of the attendance of the ERN 2022:

- Approximately 3,600 visitors attended the event as part of the afternoon program and 1,000 viewers online. In addition, around 600 pupils attended the workshops for schools in the morning.
- More than 300 scientists took part in 11 workshop formats, 6 online lectures, a science flash and a round table, 74 scientific stations, as well as the stage program with the show by Werner Gruber, 5 science slams at the Austrian final, and two concerts.

Feedback from participants (For activities that distributed questionnaires to participants)

An online questionnaire was distributed by the ERN 2020 organisers, but the results have not been shared; therefore, no feedback information is available.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.9 Winter School Training Activity Report

ERIGRID 2.0 Training Activity Report Training School – Introduction to Real-Time Digital Simulations with Applications to Sustainable Energy Systems

Overview

Hosting partner: TU Delft
 Co-organizing partners: University of Strathclyde and National Technical University of Athens
 Delivered date: 26/01/23 to 26/01/23

Type of Activity: Training Schools

Contact: Vetrivel Subramaniam Rajkumar (V.SubramaniamRajkumar@tudelft.nl)

Agenda and Schedule of the event

The training school was organized in person at TU Delft, with interactive lectures and hands-on training sessions from Jan 23 to 26, 2023:

Time	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4
08:30-09:00	Registration, welcome			
09:00-09:45	Lecture: Overview of RTDS hardware and RSCAD	Lecture: real-time modelling of wind energy systems	Lecture: HVDC & converter technologies	Lecture: advanced lab testing for future power systems
09:45-10:00	Break	Break	Break	Break
10:00-10:45	Software setup and installation	Lecture: intro to small and sub time-step modelling of wind energy systems	Lab: modelling of HVDC networks	Lecture: advanced lab testing for future power systems
10:45-12:00	Lab: building simple RSCAD models	Lab: sub time-step Groups of 3-4		Lab: HIL and CHIL applications
12:00-13:00	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch	Lunch
13:00-15:00	Lab: building simple RSCAD models	Lab: sub time-step modelling and simulation	Lab: modelling of HVDC networks	Lab: HIL and CHIL applications
15:00-15:30	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break
15:30-16:00				Plenary and closing
15:30-17:00	Lab: building simple RSCAD models	Lab: sub time-step modelling and simulation	Lab tour & MMC Demo	
19:00-			Group Dinner	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

First name	Last name	Institution	Country	Current status
Noman	Shabbir	Tallinn University of Technology	Estonia	Researcher
Corentin	Evens	VTT	Finland	Researcher
Marius	Baranauskas	VTT Technical research centre of Finland	Finland	Researcher/PhD
Muhammad	Faheem	University of Vaasa	Finland	Researcher
Moiz	Ahmed	German Aerospace Center (DLR)-Institute of Networked Energy Systems	Germany	Researcher
Kyriaki-Nefeli	Malamaki	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece	Postdoctoral Researcher
Stelios	Dimoulias	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki	Greece	PhD student
Cedric	Caruana	University of Malta	Malta	Academic Staff
Somesh	Bhattacharya	University of Malta	Malta	Researcher
Ibrahim	Diab	TU Delft	Netherlands	PhD student
Ilhami	Poyraz	Dicle University	Turkey	PhD student
Ömer Faruk	Özcan	Dicle University	Turkey	PhD student
Eleni	Tsotsopoulou	Smart Power Networks (SMPnet)	United Kingdom	Professional

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

A training school on introduction to real-time digital simulation with applications in sustainable energy systems was organized by the Intelligent Electrical Power Grids (IEPG) section of the Electrical Sustainable Energy (ESE) department at the Delft University of Technology. The training school was intended to introduce real-time power system simulations and its wide range of applications in sustainable energy systems. This includes modelling and simulation of renewables such as wind turbines and high voltage DC applications. Furthermore, the training school also touched upon the concept of Controller-hardware-in-the-loop, in collaboration with the University of Strathclyde and National Technical University of Athens.

Achievements and learning outcomes

Upon course completion, the participants were able to:

1. Model and simulate simple power system networks in RTDS.
2. Understand the concept of small-time step for detailed modelling of renewables – wind turbines and HVDC.
3. Apply real-time simulations to study and analyse power networks with high share of renewables.
4. Understand the concept of application of Hardware-in-Loop experiments

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

A.3.10 Workshop ICT for automation in smart grids

ERIGrid 2.0 Training Activity Report ICT for automation in smart grid and its cybersecurity challenges

Overview

Hosting partner: SINTEF Energy

Co-organizing partners: VTT, TUD, OFFIS, DTU

Delivered date: 30th – 31st January 2023

Type of Activity: Workshop

Contact: Tesfaye Amare/SINTEF Energy, tesfaye.zerihun@sintef.no

Agenda and Schedule of the event

Day 1 (Monday, January 30) Location: Auditorium, Staten hus, Prinsens gt. 1A, 7013 Trondheim	
Presentation title	Presenter name
Lunch (Staten hus auditorium, prinsens gate 1A, Trondheim)	
Welcome, Introduction about CINELDI and ERIGrid projects	<i>Henning Taxt, SINTEF Energy</i>
Automation in smart grid	
Keynote 1: Role of real-time virtualization in smart grid applications	Anna Kulmala, <i>R&D Project Manager, ABB</i>
Testbed for Advanced Distribution Management Systems	<i>Merkebu Z. Degefa/ Santiago Sanchez Acevedo, SINTEF Energy Research</i>
Virtualization and Management in Substations	<i>Jirapa Kamsamrong, OFFIS</i>
Coffee break	
Smart meter measurements-based topology identification in distributions network	<i>Raymundo E. Torres-Olguin, SINTEF Energy Research</i>
Data-driven monitoring of cyber-physical energy systems: enhancing resilience and security	<i>Nils Müller, DTU</i>
Comparison of different control architectures in distributions network	<i>Jonatan Klemets, SINTEF Energy Research</i>
Visit to National Smart Grid laboratory (travelling)	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Presentation/Introduction about NSGL	<i>Salvatore D. Acoro, SINTEF Energy</i>
Digital substation Intrusion detection and prevention system based on Software defined network technology	<i>Santiago Sanchez Acevedo, SINTEF Energy</i>
Dinner (Øx Tap Room, Munkegata 26, Trondheim)	

Day 2 (Tuesday, January 31) Location: Auditorium, Staten hus, Prinsen gt. 1A, 7013 Trondheim	
Presentation title	Presenter name
Welcome & registration	<i>Tesfaye Amare, SINTEF Energy</i>
Cyber-security in smart grid	
Keynote 2: Using Offensive Security Techniques to Build better Resilience into Smart Grid	<i>Prof.dr. Siv Hilde Houmb (Senior Advisor Digital Security, Statnett- Norwegian TSO)</i>
Cybersecurity of digital substations: Impact analysis on cascading failures	<i>Vetrivel Subramaniam Rajkumar, TUD</i>
Cyber-attack forensics on substation	<i>Petra Raussi, VTT</i>
Threat modeling for Smart Grid	<i>Lars Flå, SINTEF Digital</i>
Coffee break	
Examples of practical cyberattacks on the Smart Grid.	<i>Lars Flå/Martin, SINTEF Digital</i>
Autonomous Adaptive Security for 5G-enabled IoT from smart grid perspective	<i>Sandeep Pirbhulal, Norwegian Computing Centre (NR)</i>
Blockchain Support for Time-Critical Self-Healing in Smart Distribution Grids	<i>Befekadu Gebrselase, NTNU</i>
Lunch (Staten hus auditorium, prinsens gate 1A, Trondheim)	
5G for smart grid	
Keynote 3: 5G communication services for critical infrastructure operation	<i>Prof. Poul Heegaard, NTNU</i>
Edge computing for smart grid applications incl. fault indication	<i>Heli Kokkonen-Tarkkanen, VTT</i>
Coffee break	
Intent-based 5G Network Slicing for Smart Distribution Grids.	<i>Kalpanie Mendis, NTNU</i>
Data compression of SV data to decrease packet losses in 5G channel	<i>Petra Raussi, VTT</i>
Closing statement	<i>Henning Taxt, SINTEF Energy</i>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

List of participants (Only for Summer/Winter schools and workshops)

- ❖ Heli Kokkonen-Tarkkanen
- ❖ Kim Erling Rasmussen
- ❖ Nils Müller
- ❖ Trond Vatten
- ❖ Sergio Castro
- ❖ Gerthory Toussaint
- ❖ Poul Heegaard
- ❖ Henning Taxt
- ❖ Santiago Sanchez
- ❖ Siv Hilde Houmb
- ❖ Martin Bore
- ❖ Vetrivel S Rajkumar
- ❖ Henrik Lundkvist
- ❖ Danial Jafarigiv
- ❖ Lars Flå
- ❖ Geir Mathisen
- ❖ Merkebu Z. Degefa
- ❖ Hazhir Ghasemnezhad
- ❖ Martin Gilje Jaatun
- ❖ TIRUPATI SOLANKE
- ❖ Salvatore d'arco
- ❖ Tesfaye Amare
- ❖ Jonatan Klemets
- ❖ Jirapa Kamsamrong
- ❖ Petra Raussi
- ❖ Raymundo E. Torres-Olguin
- ❖ Kalpanie Mendis
- ❖ Sandeep Pirbhulal

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Short description of the event activities/ Presented topics of the event

There were 3 main sessions in the areas of automation, the use of 5G and cyber security in smart grid. Each session had a keynote speech and a number of presentations from ERIGrid and CINELDI partners. The presentations focused on sharing current research activities, experiences and the testbeds used in relation to the use of ICT for automation and the related cyber security challenges. At the end of the first day, there was also a laboratory visit and demonstration in the National Smart Grid Laboratory of SINTEF.

Achievements and learning outcomes

The participants familiarized themselves with the scope of ERIGrid project, the project partner's current research activities including the testbeds being developed in the areas of grid automation and its cyber security challenges. In addition, the participants had the possibility to engage in the Q&A sessions to further discuss and share experiences on the specified ICT related research activities.

Statistics of the event (Webinars or Virtual Workshops)

No. Registered persons: 38

No. of Attended Persons: 31

No. of Project External Persons: 21

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

More photos can be found here:

<https://aitonline.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/sites/ERIGRID2.0CollaborationEnvironment/Shared%20Documents/NA3%20-%20Education%20and%20Training/Activities/Workshops/30-31-January-2023-SINTEF%20%20Workshop/photos?csf=1&web=1&e=0vFYEI>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Appendix B: Staff Exchange Information

B.1 Documents and Forms

B.1.1 Application Form

ERIGRID 2.0 STAFF EXCHANGE APPLICATION FORM

Proposal for requesting financial support for the staff exchange between project partners

* Required

1. Staff Exchange Name *

2. Visiting Researcher's Home Organisation *

3. Visiting Researcher's Name *

4. Visiting Researcher's Email Address *

5. Visiting Researcher's Contact Details (Address, Phone Number, etc.) *

6. Estimated Exchange Begin *

7. Estimated Exchange End *

8. Host Organisation *

9. Motivation, Purpose, and Expected Results (max. 2,000 characters) *

10. Estimateed Travel and Accomodation Costs (max. 2,000 EUR) *

11. Comments, Questions, or Additional Information *

You can print a copy of your answer after you submit

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B.1.2 Summary Report Template

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGrid 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Staff Exchange Summary Report

[Staff Exchange Name (same as in proposal)]

Stay Period: dd/mm/yyyy to dd/mm/yyyy

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Visiting Researcher: [Name of the Visiting Researcher (institution name)]

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Staff Exchange Name:	[Staff Exchange Name (same as in proposal)]
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-Report-Staff-Exchange-StaffExchangeName-draft-vn.n
Report Version:	vn.n
Report Submission Date:	dd/mm/yyyy
Keywords:	[List of free keywords relevant to the report], European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	x draft, final

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
dd/mm/yyyy	v1.0	Name (Partner short name)	Draft report template

1 Staff Exchange Overview

1.1 Researcher and Host Information

Staff Exchange Information	
Staff Exchange Name	[Staff Exchange Name (same as in proposal)]
Visiting Researcher Home Org.	[Visiting Researcher Home Organisation Name (same as in proposal)]
Visiting Researcher Name	[Visiting Researcher Name (same as in proposal)]
Host Organisation	[Host Organisation Name (same as in proposal)]
Stay Period	[dd/mm/yyyy to dd/mm/yyyy]

1.2 Motivation and Purpose

TODO: “This section should briefly outline the motivation and purpose of the staff exchange; the description from the application form can be used. The description should be no longer than half a page.”

2 Main Outcomes and Lessons Learned

2.1 Results

TODO: “This section should briefly outline the main achievements and results of the performed staff exchange. The stay should be documented also with corresponding photo material which might be included in the appendix. The description should be no longer than a page.”

2.2 Lessons Learned

TODO: “This section should briefly outline the lessons learned from the performed staff exchange. The description should be no longer than a page.”

3 Conclusions

TODO: “This section should provide the main conclusions of the performed staff exchange. The description should be no longer than half a page.”

Appendix A. Document Guidelines

A.1. Report Titles

Reports have a title that is defined in the submitted Staff Exchange Application Form. Please stick to the official spelling.

A.2. File Naming

The project will generate many documents (reports) and versions of these reports. It is beneficial to consistently use an agreed file naming format.

ERIGrid2-Report-Staff-Exchange-StaffExchangeName-Status-vn.n.Extension

- Notice the hyphen between the various elements of the file name.
- **ERIGrid2:** Each ERIGrid 2.0 report should be preceded by the project acronym. Notice, there is only one correct spelling of the acronym, i.e., 'ERIGrid 2.0', but for file names 'ERIGrid2' will be used.
- **StaffExchangeName:** This should be based on the information that has been provided in the Staff Exchange Application Form.
- **Status:**
 - *draft* = Draft Version – indicates that the drafting of the report is in progress;
 - *final* = Final Version as checked and updated by the User Group (UG) and the hosting institution;
 - *submitted* = submitted version as submitted to the ERIGrid 2.0 Project Coordinator (CO).
- **vn.n:** The version of the report starting from v1.0.
- **Extension:** File extension, e.g., 'docx' for Microsoft Word and 'pdf' for Portable Document Format.

Examples:

- ERIGrid2-Report-Lab-Access-User-Project-116-GRIDPV100-draft-v1.2.docx
- ERIGrid2-Report-Lab-Access-User-Project-116-GRIDPV100-submitted-v1.8.pdf

A.3. Change Log

The Change Log is there to keep track of the changes made to the document. Whenever changes are made to the document, a new version should be created and the changes should be briefly summarised in the Change Log. We anticipate a minimum of three phases of Change Log entries. (1) The researcher responsible for the given report enters the changes as he/she develops the document. (2) The two reviewers register the changes made in the quality assurance phase. Once the responsible researcher passes the report on to the hosting institution, the status should be changed from 'draft' to 'final'.

A.4. Document Formatting

A.4.1. Headings

Like in many journals and books, it is a good practice not to use more than 3 levels of headings. If you really need more, then by all means do so, but you may first consider how to structure the document with a maximum of three heading levels.

Use the following capitalisation style for all headings: All terms should be capitalised and do not use a full stop at the end.

A.4.2. Captions and Citations

Use the following for captions and cross referencing:

- 'Table 1' for tables, not 'table 1' or 'Tab. 1', etc.
- 'Figure 1' for figures, not 'figure 1' or 'Fig. 1', etc.
- 'Section 1.1.1' to cross-reference other sections, not 'section 1.1.1' or 'S. 1.1.1', etc.

Do not abbreviate the word 'Equation' to 'eq', 'Eqn', etc.

Table captions should be placed above the table and figure captions should be placed below the figure. The captions should succinctly describe the content of the table or figure.

A.4.3. Tables

Producing informative tables is not easy. Avoid grid lines around each table cells (typical for people with little experience in drafting technical papers). The table below (Table 1) is a good example how tables should look like. Make sure that caption appears on the same page as the table. The table caption is above the table!

The table caption should follow the sentence style layout and end with a full stop. The caption as well as the table should be centred.

Each table must be introduced in the deliverable text. Make sure that cross references to tables are correct before submitting the deliverable.

The same (simplified) table using the Word table feature is shown below (Table 2).

A.4.4. Figures

Good figures/diagrams are even more difficult to produce than tables. Figures should contain legends explaining the symbols in the figure. Avoid surrounding the figure with a box outline. If there are different parts of a figure (e.g., (a), (b), (c)), indicate these clearly. Make sure that the labels within a figure/diagram are spelled consistently within the figure/diagram and are also consistently spelled in the text. Make sure that caption appears on the same page as the figure. The figure caption is below the figure. See an example of a figure and its caption below (Figure 1).

Table 1: Summary of properties of different modelling formalisms. The table below is inserted as graphic.

	Static (s), dynamic (d)	Discrete (d), continuous (c)	Deterministic (d), stochastic (s)	Qualitative (ql), quantitative (qn)	Coarse (c), average (a), fine (f) grained
DG	s		d	ql	c
BYN	s ^a	d,c	s	qn	c
BNN	d	d	d	ql	c
GLN	d	d	d	ql	a
NLDE	d	c	d	qn	a,f
PLDE	d	c	d	ql,qn ^c	a
QDE	d	d	d	ql	a,f
PDE	d	c ^b	d	qn	a,f
SME	d	d	s	qn	f
R	d	d	d	ql	a,f

^aGeneralization to dynamic Boolean networks is possible.

^bSpatial dimension is often discretized.

^cQualitative analysis of models is possible.

Table 2: Summary of properties of different modelling formalisms. The table below is produced using Word table environment.

	Static	Discrete	Deterministic	Qualitative	Coarse
DG	s		d	ql	c
BYN	s	d,c	s	qn	c
BNN	d	d	d	ql	c
GLN	d	c	d	qn	a,f

Each figure must be introduced in the deliverable text. Make sure that cross references to figures are correct before submitting the deliverable.

The figure caption should follow the sentence style layout and end with a full stop. The figure caption as well as the figure should be centred.

Figure 1: Caption caption caption caption caption caption caption caption caption. (a) Caption caption caption, (b) Caption caption caption, (c) Caption caption caption.

A.4.5. Footnotes

This¹ is a footnote.

¹The footnote is at the bottom of the same page where the footnote is cited and the font size is only 9 pt. Footnotes are useful to for including nasty-looking long Web references which would look terrible if used in the main flow of the text.

A.5. Language and Notation

There are a few things we should consider when writing documents in terms of language. The question is not deeply philosophical in the sense of whether one or the other approach is fundamentally correct (or wrong). It is more the case of maintaining a certain level of consistency across the project.

Since British/UK English is the official version of English within the European Commission (EC), we should by default use UK English spelling (and adopt a spell-checker set to UK English). Nevertheless, US spelling is also fine – the main issue to ensure is to be consistent within a given deliverable.

Quotation marks. UK English (unlike US), use single quotation marks ('X') instead of double quotation marks ("X"). At least maintain consistency within a document.

- It is claimed that Y is 'superior' to X.
- 'Good morning, Dave,' greeted HAL.

Do not use quotation marks to indicate emphasis – use italics, bold or underline style instead.

The accepted standard for separating orders of magnitude in large figures is not ', ' or "" (quotation mark) or '.', but a non-breaking (small) space.

- This is inappropriate: 1,000,000 or 1.000.000 or 1'000'000 (very bad!)
- This is good: 1 000 000.

Capitalisation. Use capitalisation according to English grammar rules. If someone is interested, see capitalisation rules:²

Tense. Use past tense when describing activities and tasks (experiments, developments, etc) carried out in the past.

- A test bed was set up to ...
- The evaluation revealed that ...

Use present tense when describing the ideas, design, systems, etc. that exist in the present.

- The system supports the following exchange formats ...
- A key property of the system is its ability to ...

Large numbers. Use explicit format or scientific notation for large numbers

- Use 1 200 000 000, not 1.2bn or 1,200,000,000
- Or use 1.20 10⁹ or 1.20 × 10⁹

Small numbers. As usual, unless in tables and similar elements, use one, two, ..., twelve for numbers < 13, and 13, 14, ..., for large numbers.

Numbers and units. Use space to separate figures from units. E.g.,

- 10 GB, not 10GB
- 2.13 s not 2.13s

²<http://andromeda.rutgers.edu/~jlynch/Writing/c.html>, <http://www.grammarbook.com/punctuation/capital.asp>

Bits, bytes and pieces. Use the following terms and abbreviations for bytes (sometimes it is better to use the full term than the abbreviation).

Bits:

kb or Kb	kilobit	10 ³
Mb	megabit	10 ⁶
Gb	gigabit	10 ⁹
Tb	terabit	10 ¹²

Bytes:

kB or KB	kilobyte	10 ³
MB	megabyte	10 ⁶
GB	gigabyte	10 ⁹
TB	terabyte	10 ¹²

Number of decimals. When a number is expressed in the scientific notation, the number of significant digits (or significant figures) is the number of digits needed to express the number to within the uncertainty of calculation. For example, if a quantity is known to be 1.234 ± 0.002 , four figures would be significant³.

Unless there is a good reason, do not use more than three fractional digits or places (the number of digits following the point).

Other issues. Avoid overly long sentences. Certain rules suggest that sentence over approximately 20 words become difficult to understand and should therefore be avoided.

A.6. Formatting Bibliographical References

By default, references should use APA style (as, e.g., used in Google Scholar) and be ordered in alphabetic order. See for example (Tan, Kumar, & Srivastava, 2004), in the list below.

Other styles are also OK, nevertheless the authors should make sure that within a single document the notation to references and their citation should be consistent. In the text, the references should ideally be referred to by the author name and year, e.g., (Lampert, 1994); however, referencing by reference number is also acceptable.

A.7. Associated Outputs

If appropriate, please include a section with details of any datasets, code or other resources being released with this report.

The work described in this report has resulted in the following resources:

Description	URL	Availability
My Dataset 1	http://hdl.handle.net/12345	Public (Apache 2.0)
My Dataset 2	http://hdl.handle.net/54321	Private (consortium only)
My Code	github.com/erigrid2/xxx	Public (GPL3)

³ <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/SignificantDigits.html>

Appendix B. Heading

B.1. Heading

TODO: "Explain the content of the appendix."

B.2. Heading

TODO: "Explain the content of the appendix."

Appendix C. Heading

C.1. Heading

TODO: "Explain the content of the appendix."

C.2. Heading

TODO: "Explain the content of the appendix."

Consortium

Disclaimer

All information provided reflects the status of the ERIGrid 2.0 project at the time of writing and may be subject to change.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

B.1.3 Cost Reimbursement Sheet Template

H2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project (870620)

ERIGrid 2.0 Staff Exchange Manager

AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH
 Center for Energy - Electric Energy Systems
 att. Dr. Thomas Strasser (Coordinator ERIGrid 2.0)
 Giefinggasse 4
 1210 Vienna, Austria

Visiting Researcher Information

NAME	< First Name, Last Name >
HOME ORGANISATION	< Official Name of Organization >
EMAIL ADDRESS	< Contact Email Address >
POSTAL ADDRESS	< Address line one, e.g., street name, street number > < Address line two, e.g., postal code city, country >
PHONE NUMBER	< Contact Phone Number >
VAT REGISTRATION NUMBER *	

Hosting Organisation Information

HOST ORGANISATION	< Official Name of Organization >
PERIOD OF STAY	< dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy >
NUMBER OF STAY DAYS	< dd >

**ERIGrid 2.0 STAFF EXCHANGE
INVOICE / EXPENSE SHEET**

When filled in and signed, please send your scanned invoice together with the technical report to mgt@erigrd2.eu

DATE: 26 April 2023

EXPENSES

#	Description	Dates	Net Sum (without VAT)	Sum	Document
1	< Plane ticket >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0,00	0,00	< Invoice n° ... >
2	< Hotel xxx >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0,00	0,00	< PDF file (scanned tickets) >
3	< Public transport xxx >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0,00	0,00	< ... >
4	< ... >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0,00	0,00	< ... >
5	< ... >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0,00	0,00	< ... >
...	< ... >	dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy	0,00	0,00	< ... >
Total			-	-	EUR

Visiting Researcher Signature

RESEARCHERS SIGNATURES INSTITUTION'S STAMP *	< Signature > < First Name, Last Name >
--	--

Bank Details for Reimbursement

NAME OF THE BANK	
SUBJECT/COMMENT	
ADDRESS OF THE BANK	
ACCOUNT HOLDER NAME	
IBAN ACCOUNT NUMBER	
BIC (SWIFT) CODE	

* If non applicable, leave it blank.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870620.

B.1.4 Payment Receipt Template

		ERIGrid 2.0 STAFF EXCHANGE PAYMENT RECEIPT <small>When filled in and signed, please send your scanned invoice together with the technical report to mgt@erigrd2.eu</small>	
H2020 ERIGrid 2.0 Project (870620)			
<i>ERIGrid 2.0 Staff Exchange Manager</i>			
AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH Center for Energy - Electric Energy Systems att. Dr. Thomas Strasser (Coordinator ERIGrid 2.0) Giefinggasse 4 1210 Vienna, Austria		DATE: 26 April 2023	
<i>Visiting Researcher Information</i>			
NAME	< First Name, Last Name >		
HOME ORGANISATION	< Official Name of Organization >		
EMAIL ADDRESS	< Contact Email Address >		
POSTAL ADDRESS	< Address line one, e.g., street name, street number > < Address line two, e.g., postal code city, country >		
PHONE NUMBER	< Contact Phone Number >		
VAT REGISTRATION NUMBER *			
<i>Hosting Organisation Information</i>			
HOST ORGANISATION	< Official Name of Organization >		
PERIOD OF STAY	< dd/mm/yyyy - dd/mm/yyyy >		
NUMBER OF STAY DAYS	< dd >		
CONFIRMATION OF PAYMENT			
AMOUNT (in EUR)	< Include total amount of received reimbursements (according to the submitted expense sheet) >		
DESCRIPTION	< Include short and meaningful description (e.g., staff exchange reimbursement for application #'x' hosted at 'Official Name of Hosting Institution'. >		
<i>Lab Access User Group Signatures</i>			
USER GROUP MEMBER'S SIGNATURES INSTITUTION'S STAMP *	< Signature > < First Name, Last Name >		
<small>* If non applicable, leave it blank.</small>			
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 870620.			

B.2 Activity Reports

In the following pages, the activity reports of the realised staff exchanges are included. They describe the performed tasks in detail.

B.2.1 Activity Report 1 - Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGrid 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Staff Exchange Summary Report

Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation

Stay Period: 23/06/2022 to 30/06/2022

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Visiting Researcher: Alexandros Paspatis (ICCS-NTUA), Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Staff Exchange Name:	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2.0 Staff Exchange Report VSIDC Final
Report Version:	v2.0
Report Submission Date:	09/07/2022
Keywords:	Hardware-in-the-Loop, Delay Compensation, Interface Algorithm, DRTS, Laboratory Testing, Power Systems, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	Final

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
04/07/2022	v1.0	Alexandros Paspatis (ICCS-NTUA), Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA)	First version of staff exchange report
09/07/2022	v2.0	Alexandros Paspatis (ICCS-NTUA), Alkistis Kontou (ICCS-NTUA)	Final version of staff exchange report

1 Staff Exchange Overview

1.1 Researcher and Host Information

Staff Exchange Information	
Staff Exchange Name	Virtual Shifting Impedance with Delay Compensation
Visiting Researcher Home Org.	ICCS-NTUA
Visiting Researcher Name	Alexandros Paspatis, Alkistis Kontou
Host Organisation	University of Strathclyde
Stay Period	23/06/2022 to 30/06/2022

1.2 Motivation and Purpose

ICCS, UoS and CEA have developed as part of JRA2.2 a novel Interface Algorithm (IA) for Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (PHIL) simulations that improves stability and accuracy, two important metrics for utilizing PHIL simulations. PHIL has proven to be an advanced method for validation of smart grid technologies in controlled laboratory environment, howbeit the testing is under conditions pretty close to actual field testing.

The developed interface algorithm, called Virtual Shifting Impedance (VSI) builds on proven existing algorithms, and virtually introduces a shifting impedance into the coupling topology of the DRTS and the HUT, through the controller of the amplifier. This IA, lends the characteristics and properties of the Physical Shifting Impedance (PSI) method, as well as the virtual impedance technique that in principle provides additional damping to a system. VSI expands the applicability of PSI and the limitations of this method, which concerns the availability of variable hardware impedances at hand. Thus, the shifting part of the impedance can virtually introduced in the controller of an amplifier, eliminating the need of hardware availability.

The main purpose of the staff exchange was to validate the stability and accuracy properties of this method through simulations and experiments. The widely applicable feedback filter method was considered as the baseline scenario for the comparison. Moreover, using a delay compensation method was considered, to test if accuracy can be further improved. Furthermore, the experiments are related to the demonstrations to be implemented in the frame of ERIGrid 2.0 JRA4 work package. Ultimately, a paper publication is currently under progress.

2 Main Outcomes and Lessons Learned

2.1 Results

As it was highlighted earlier, the main purpose of this staff exchange was to perform an elaborate accuracy analysis, in order to compare the proposed novel interface algorithms in comparison to benchmark approaches, as well as work on the experimental validation of the proposed algorithm.

With regards to the first task, an advanced simulation model was built, which apart of dynamically simulating the the proposed and the benchmark interface algorithms, it is also capturing different accuracy metrics which can be employed for the accuracy analysis. In particular, these metrics correspond to error functions of voltage, current and powers both during the steady-state and transient events.

Figure 1 Simulation model with accuracy metrics

In the following table, indicative results are shown for the benchmark feedback filtering method, as well as the proposed VSI algorithm. To perform a fair comparison, the delay compensation part is not implemented in any method, while two different forms of the VSI algorithm, the dynamic and the steady-state one are investigated for their applicability. An indicative scenario simulated during the Staff Exchange is presented in the following table, where the achieved accuracy metrics for feedback filtering method (benchmark method), transient VSI (proposed method #1) and steady-state VSI (proposed method #2).

Table 1 Indicative accuracy results for the benchmark and proposed methods

	Benchmark	Method #1	Method #2
Steady-state power tracking error	1.64 %	2.54 %	1.27 %

Finally, Method #2 was built into the controller of the power amplifier of the DPSL laboratory and initial investigations were performed, towards the complete testing that will be performed as part of Demo 1 of the JRA4 work package of ERIGrid 2.0 project.

2.2 Lessons Learned

The staff exchange under reporting brought into an a closer collaboration two research teams that were already working together in various work packages of the ERIGrid 2.0 project. Based on the active collaboration and the fruitful discussions during this research visit, the following lessons learned can be drawn:

- First of all, the researchers from ICCS were familiarized with the topic of accuracy analysis of PHIL simulations, with the support of research from the home institution, University of Strathclyde who were already experienced with this topic.
- Moreover, both research teams collaboratively investigated the concept of accuracy analysis during transient events and implemented advanced accuracy analysis metrics to conclude about the interface algorithms under consideration.
- In a more technical manner, through the aforementioned investigation of the accuracy analysis, it was identified that the virtual shifting impedance method using a steady-state approximation is more appropriate for the accuracy needs of PHIL simulations, rather than the full dynamic model of the virtual impedance that needs a low-pass filter to guarantee stability.
- Additionally, plans and topics for future research and the expansion of the collaboration between UoS and ICCS-NTUA were discussed.
- Finally, the two teams exchanged knowledge with regards to new trends in laboratory equipment and discussed the planned updates of the laboratories of their institutions.

Both the home and visiting organizations' teams found the Staff Exchange Opportunity really useful and agreed to further utilize such opportunities for supporting the work of the ERIGrid 2.0 project.

3 Conclusions

During this staff exchange, researchers from ICCS-NTUA visited the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory of the University of Strathclyde (UoS). The two research teams had been collaborating actively throughout many work packages of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, and the opportunity for this staff exchange further supported the work performed throughout JRA2 and JRA4 work packages.

In particular, the two research teams, had the opportunity to perform an advanced accuracy analysis to compare different novel methods that were under consideration for achieving a stable and accurate PHIL simulation. Moreover, the method that ended up to outperform the others was subject to initial experimental testing, while further validation will be performed through the Demo 1 of the JRA4 work package.

Finally, apart from the technical developments, this staff exchange brought the two research teams closer and initiated further discussions on topics for common future research as well as knowledge exchange between the plans of the two institutions for upgrading their laboratory facilities.

Appendix A. Photos from the staff exchange

Figure 2 ICCS-NTUA and UoS researchers working together

Figure 3 ICCS-NTUA and UoS researchers working together

Figure 4 UoS team welcoming ICCS-NTUA team

Consortium

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B.2.2 Activity Report 2 - JRA3 – Universal API Development and Testing

European Research Infrastructure supporting Smart Grid and Smart Energy Systems Research, Technology Development, Validation and Roll Out – Second Edition

Project Acronym: **ERIGRID 2.0**

Project Number: **870620**

Staff Exchange Summary Report

JRA3 – Universal API development and testing

Stay Period: 12/12/2022 to 14/12/2022

Funding Instrument: Research and Innovation Action
Call: H2020-INFRAIA-2019-1
Call Topic: INFRAIA-01-2018-2019 Integrating Activities for Advanced Communities

Project Start: 1 April 2020
Project Duration: 54 months

Visiting Researchers: Steffen (RWTH), Edmund (AIT), Oliver (DTU), Gabriele (RSE), John (CRES), Mikael (VTT), Pham (CEA), Le Minh Tri (CEA), Jose (TEC), Pratyush (OFFIS)

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 870620.

Report Information

Document Administrative Information	
Project Acronym:	ERIGrid 2.0
Project Number:	870620
Staff Exchange Name:	JRA3 – Universal API development and testing
Document Identifier:	ERIGrid2-Report-Staff-Exchange-StaffExchangeName-draft-vn.n
Report Version:	V2.0
Report Submission Date:	13/02/2023
Keywords:	API, middleware, data-exchange, European Union (EU), H2020, Project, ERIGrid 2.0, GA 870620
Status:	Final

Change Log

Date	Version	Author/Editor	Summary of Changes Made
27/01/2023	v1.0	Vetri (TUD)	Draft report template
13/02/2023	V2.0	Vetri (TUD)	Finalize

1 Staff Exchange Overview

1.1 Researcher and Host Information

Staff Exchange Information	
Staff Exchange Name	JRA3 – Universal API development and testing
Visiting Researcher Home Orgs.	RWTH, AIT, DTU, TEC, RSE, CRES, CEA, and VTT
Visiting Researcher Name	Steffen Vogel, Edmund Widl, Oliver Gehrke, Gabriele Paludetto, John Nikolettatos, Pratyush Das, Mikael Opas, Pham Minh Cong, Le Minh Tri, Jose Antonio López
Host Organisation	TUD
Stay Period	12/12/2022 to 14/12/2022

1.2 Motivation and Purpose

The JRA3 staff exchange was aimed at further development and release of the universal API (uAPI) v2.0 developed within the scope of JRA3 middleware. The uAPI forms the basis for the lab middleware and data exchange service to be further used in the JRA4 demos. The major purposes of the staff exchange were as follows:

1. Update uAPI with changes as documented in github
2. Implement uAPI v2 in transports tools: VILLAS, JanDER, and Lablink
3. Test new version of uAPI

2 Main Outcomes and Lessons Learned

2.1 Results

As previously mentioned, the main goals of the staff exchange were to update the uAPI to v2. Furthermore, the next goal was to implement its support in the most commonly used lab-coupling tools, within the ERIGrid context, i.e., VILLAS, JanDER, and Lablink. Both these tasks have been successfully achieved post the staff exchange. The figure highlights the landing webpage for the documentation of the uAPI, keeping in line with the openAPI specification. The uAPI is summarized as a, “common API used by ERIGrid research infrastructures to exchange signals for geographically distributed experiments.” Furthermore, two of the data-exchange tools/transports have already implemented v2 of the uAPI – VILLAS Framework and AIT Lablink.

A dedicated github repository contains all the code development and associated documentation: <https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA-3.1-api>.

Figure 1: uAPI description webpage.

2.2 Lessons Learned

The major takeaways/lessons learned from the staff exchange were as follows:

- Smaller working groups/breakout sessions turned out to be productive and helpful. This was especially crucial for fruitful brainstorming, development, and debugging.
- Code examples/documentation greatly simplify the process of performing joint experiments, especially for partners without significant ICT knowledge/background.
- To improve adoption and usage of the uAPI, it was decided to provide some code samples and paradigms. This will prove to be useful to partners not involved in JRA3, but only in the JRA4 demos.

3 Conclusions

In summary, the JRA3 staff exchange aimed to further develop and release the uAPI v2.0 as part of the JRA3 middleware development. The uAPI will serve as the foundation for the lab middleware and data exchange service for JRA4 demos. The staff exchange focused on updating the uAPI to handle new data types, implementing it in transport tools (VILLAS, JanDER, and Lablink), and testing the new version of the uAPI. The staff exchange was successful in fostering greater collaborations and discussions within JRA3 and ERIGrid 2.

Appendix A. Photos from Staff Exchange

Figure 2 Staff exchange researchers working together

Figure 3 Staff-exchange group photo. Researchers from left to right: CEA,RSE,TEC,CRES,TUD,DTU,RWTH,AIT,OFFIS, and VTT

Appendix B. Outputs

The work described in this report has resulted in the following resource

Description	URL	Availability
uAPI repository	https://github.com/ERIGrid2/JRA-3.1-api	Public (GPL3)

JRA3 – Universal API development and testing

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